

1 **Hybrid ground-motion model for potential induced seismicity at**
2 **the Prinos CO₂ storage site (northern Greece)**

3

4 **Marco Pilz^{1,*}, Anastasia Kiratzi², Nikos Vavlas², Nikos Anterriotis-Kalpakidis²**

5 1 Helmholtz Center for Geosciences GFZ, Telegrafenberg, 14473 Potsdam, Germany

6 2 Aristotle University of Thessaloniki, Faculty of Sciences, Department of Geophysics,
7 54124 Thessaloniki, Greece

8

9

10 **Corresponding author**

11 Marco Pilz

12 Helmholtz Center for Geosciences GFZ

13 Telegrafenberg

14 14473 Potsdam

15 Germany

16 Phone: +49 331 288 28661

17 Email: pilz@gfz.de

18

19

20 **Conflict of interest statement**

21 The authors acknowledge that there are no conflicts of interest recorded.

22

23

24

25 **KEY POINTS**

- 26 • Limited data and a complex shallow crust challenge accurate prediction of induced
27 seismicity ground motion.
- 28 • We develop the first physics-guided hybrid GMM for the Prinos CO₂ storage site
29 in northern Greece.
- 30 • The GMM integrates machine learning-enhanced data and stochastic simulations
31 via mixed-effects regression.

32

33 **ABSTRACT**

34

35 Reports of seismicity linked to human activities have become increasingly common over
36 the past few decades, yet predicting the level of ground motion generated by induced
37 earthquakes remains challenging due to limited observational data and the variable
38 structure of the upper crust. Reliable ground motion models (GMMs) that reflect region-
39 specific seismological conditions are therefore essential for the proper assessment of
40 induced seismic hazard. Existing GMMs, derived primarily from tectonic events, are not
41 necessarily applicable to shallow, low-to-moderate magnitude induced earthquakes, for
42 which source, path, and site effects may differ substantially. In this study, we develop the
43 first region-specific hybrid ground-motion model specifically designed for potential
44 injection-induced seismicity at the Prinos CO₂ storage site in northern Greece. The
45 modelling framework combines stochastic simulations calibrated against available
46 regional recordings and constrained by an *a-priori* seismological model. GMM parameters

47 are then optimized through iterative calibration and epistemic parametric uncertainty is
48 quantified by retaining suites of acceptable parameter combinations. A synthetic dataset
49 combining region-specific empirical recordings and simulated events covering
50 magnitudes $2 \leq M_w \leq 6$ and hypocentral distances up to 80 km allows comparison with
51 existing GMMs for induced seismicity. The final hybrid model integrates simulated
52 motions with an expanded empirical dataset that includes machine learning-derived
53 seismic events. The resulting GMM provides a regionally calibrated framework for
54 ground-motion modelling and hazard assessment at the Prinos storage site and
55 contributes to ongoing efforts to develop methodologies for quantifying the ground-
56 motion characteristics of induced earthquakes in Europe.

57

58 **Keywords:** Induced seismicity, stochastic simulations, hybrid-calibrated ground motion
59 model

60

61

62 INTRODUCTION

63 As carbon capture and storage (CCS) projects expand across Europe, identifying and
64 qualifying safe and reliable storage sites is crucial. This requires a thorough assessment of
65 geological reservoirs formed in diverse tectonic and geophysical settings. A key concern
66 is that the injection of substantial volumes of CO₂ into the subsurface can increase pore
67 pressure in the reservoir, thereby potentially (re-)activating pre-existing deep basement
68 faults, many of which are often unmapped (e.g., [Rutqvist et al., 2016](#)). Consequently,
69 induced seismicity, particularly in seismically active regions, is a primary concern that
70 could hinder public acceptance of CCS technologies. Both project proponents and
71 regulators must therefore address this issue.

72 One of the essential elements in quantifying the hazard and the potential consequences
73 of such earthquakes on exposed population and building stock are ground motion models
74 (GMMs). Selecting appropriate GMMs that reliably assess the level of ground motion for
75 the specific seismotectonic context in the region and magnitude range of interest is
76 crucial for a credible seismic hazard assessment. The reason for this is that induced
77 earthquakes are generally of smaller magnitude and shallower focal depth than the
78 ranges typically covered by GMMs derived for tectonic seismicity. Moreover, stress drop,
79 which controls the strength of ground motion at high frequencies, increases with focal
80 depth (and magnitude), leading to relatively weak radiation from the source for shallow
81 induced events compared to deeper tectonic events ([Yenier and Atkinson, 2015](#)). Another
82 challenge in developing GMMs for induced earthquakes is that, since these events are
83 typically of lower magnitude and shallower depth, regional variations in seismic wave

84 propagation and attenuation become increasingly pronounced. ([Chiou et al., 2010](#)). All
85 these factors indicate that ground motions from induced seismicity are more likely to
86 exhibit differences from one location or region to another, compared to the case for
87 natural earthquakes. Accordingly, the development of event-specific GMMs is
88 recommended, as the direct application of existing generic equations may not adequately
89 capture the source, path, and site effects associated with induced earthquakes.

90 Over the past two decades, the expansion of seismic instrumentation has led to a
91 significant increase in the volume of recorded ground motions. With the emergence of
92 large datasets containing multiple recordings from individual stations and events, the
93 characterization of the ground-motion field is beginning to shift away from strict reliance
94 on the ergodic assumption toward a more relaxed non-ergodic framework (see an
95 overview by [Lavrentiadis et al., 2023](#)). A widely adopted strategy in engineering
96 seismology is to adjust GMMs formulated for tectonically active regions to better
97 represent the seismological properties of the target area. This strategy employs
98 simulations constrained by source, path and site parameters inferred from local weak-
99 motion recordings or other relevant observational datasets. These calibrated models
100 should then suppress the impact of inherent systematic differences in the target regions
101 (e.g., [Cotton et al., 2006](#); [Bommer et al., 2010](#); [Edwards and Douglas, 2013](#); [Bommer and](#)
102 [Stafford, 2020](#)). It should, however, be noted that such adjustment must be performed
103 cautiously and accompanied by a thorough assessment of the available data as any blind
104 parametric adaption of existing GMMs is unlikely to yield a robust solution and may
105 instead lead to over-fitting of sparse local datasets.

106 In regions with demands for seismological or engineering applications but with lack of
107 recorded ground motions, complementary indirect approaches are favored, i.e., the
108 GMM is not solely derived from direct regression on recorded ground motions. Such
109 procedures frequently entail the use of simulations of ground motions, typically based on
110 a functional description of the amplitude spectrum with a random phase spectrum. These
111 approaches, which have often been named stochastic simulations and which have
112 originally been developed for tectonic earthquakes (e.g., [EPRI, 1993](#); [Schneider et al.,
113 1993](#); [Toro et al., 1997](#); [Atkinson and Boore, 2006](#); [Rietbrock et al., 2013](#); [Drouet and
114 Cotton, 2015](#); [Shahjouei and Pezeshk, 2016](#); [Liu et al., 2025](#)), have recently also
115 increasingly been applied to induced seismicity (e.g., [Edwards et al., 2019](#); [Bommer et al.,
116 2022](#); [Suroyo et al., 2024](#)). A stochastic model of earthquake ground motion is predicated
117 on the fundamental premise that simplified, yet physically based, representations of
118 energy release and seismic wave propagation for given values of earthquake size, depth
119 and distance to site will allow (taking into account the various existing uncertainties, [Liou
120 and Abrahamson, 2025](#)) allow obtaining well constrained ground motions, in turn
121 enabling the development of event-specific ground motion models.

122 Here, we outline the development of a physically-guided hybrid GMM for induced
123 seismicity associated with the subsurface CO₂ storage in the partially depleted Prinos oil
124 reservoir in northern Greece. The overall strategy is adopted from [Suroyo et al. \(2024\)](#)
125 but several methodological adaptations are tailored to the study area. In particular, we
126 place stronger emphasis on the physical calibration of the simulation framework using a
127 region-specific seismological model to capture both amplitude scaling and frequency-

128 dependent attenuation characteristics. The first stage therefore focuses on the
129 calibration of key simulation parameters controlling source, path and site effects. By
130 comparing simulated and recorded ground motions of shallow regional earthquakes, the
131 model parameters are iteratively refined. Epistemic parametric uncertainty is then
132 explored by retaining several acceptable parameter subsets that reproduce the observed
133 spectral amplitudes within confidence limits. These parameter sets are subsequently used
134 to generate a synthetic dataset for events with $M_w \leq 6$ at hypocentral distances up to
135 80 km.

136 In contrast to approaches that rely primarily on simulations alone, the hybrid GMM is
137 derived by combining the simulated dataset with available empirical observations,
138 including both manually analyzed earthquakes and additional machine learning-derived
139 events. This two-tier strategy allows the physical calibration of the stochastic model to
140 remain independent of the regression stage while stabilizing magnitude scaling through
141 an expanded observational dataset. After testing several existing GMMs for induced
142 seismicity for their suitability to the Prinos site conditions, we derive a regionally
143 calibrated hybrid GMM through mixed-effects regression using the combined synthetic
144 and empirical datasets. Scenario calculations demonstrate that the resulting model
145 provides a region-specific tool for rapid ground-motion estimation in support of hazard
146 assessments associated with potential CO₂ injection operations.

147

148

149 **THE TARGET SITE**

150 The oil extraction facilities of Prinos, located in the sea bay of Kavala on northern Greece,
151 have been proposed for the long-term sequestration and storage of CO₂ emissions from
152 both remote sources and local industries. The Prinos-Kavala basin is a fault-bounded
153 (taphrogenic) depression covering approximately 38 × 20 km (~800 km²), extending
154 mainly offshore between Thassos Island and the mainland, with a smaller onshore portion
155 in the Nestos River Delta Plain (**Figure 1**).

156 Its depocenter contains up to 5,800 m of sediments, ranging from the Lower Miocene to
157 Pleistocene, divided into three main geological units over the metamorphic basement.
158 The site has been already identified as a potential storage site nearly two decades ago
159 ([Koukouzas et al., 2009](#)) and subsequent further investigations have been carried out
160 ([e.g., Koukouzas et al., 2016; Arvanitis et al., 2020; Avraam and Vatalis, 2023](#)). In the
161 context of geological investigation, paleoclimate and sedimentological studies have
162 extracted drilled core samples and long piston cores (20 to 30 m), thus offering detailed
163 descriptions of deep sedimentary layers ([e.g., Proedrou and Sidiropoulos, 1992; Proedrou](#)
164 [and Papaconstantinou, 2004](#)). In particular, the well logs showed that the velocities at the
165 surface are close to reference rock conditions (i.e., *S*-wave velocities in uppermost tens
166 of meters in the order of 760 m/s).

167

168

169 **Figure 1:** Geographical setting of the Prinos Complex (gray area polyline) and CO₂ storage
 170 site (inner polyline) within the northern Aegean Sea, fault structures (bold lines) taken
 171 from the fault database of the Global Earthquake Model (Styron and Pagani, 2020) and
 172 instrumental (after 1911) seismicity (white circles scaled with magnitude size). All
 173 earthquakes have moderate magnitudes ($M \leq 5$). Beach balls denote the few available
 174 focal mechanisms for the area of interest (light color: normal faulting; dark color: strike-
 175 slip faulting). The color version of this figure is available only in the electronic edition.
 176 Alt text: Topographical map around the Prinos Complex within a radius of around 50 km
 177 showing the spatial distribution of seismicity.
 178

179 Although the area is characterized by faults with a significant strike-slip component that
 180 developed within the north-south extensional regime of the Aegean region (see also
 181 **Figure 1**), the Prinos-Kavala basin and the adjacent Miocene basins have not been
 182 affected and the offshore Prinos-Kavala basin appears to be relatively tectonically stable

183 (Higgins and Higgins, 1996; Koukouvelas and Aydin, 2002). While Greece is the most
184 seismically active region in Europe and therefore the European country with the highest
185 level of seismic hazard, the corresponding hazard levels in Eastern Macedonia and Thrace,
186 where the Prinos site is located, is moderate (Sotiriadis et al., 2023) compared to other
187 parts of the country. According to the European Seismic Hazard Model 2020, the
188 reference rock peak ground acceleration (PGA_{rock}) is approximately 0.13 g for a return
189 period of 475 years (Danciu et al., 2021).

190

191

192 **DATABASE OF RECORDINGS**

193 The observational dataset used for the calibration of the seismological model consists of
194 a curated set of 54 shallow ($h \leq 7$ km) earthquakes recorded between January 2008 and
195 May 2025 within a radius of 50 km around the Prinos storage site covering magnitudes in
196 the range 0.6 to 3.5 and epicentral distances in the range 4 to 237 km (see **Figure 2** and
197 **Supplementary Figures S1 to S3**). The 50 km radius was selected (1) to ensure regional
198 homogeneity of crustal structure and attenuation properties, (2) to exclude distant events
199 affected by different path characteristics and (3) to remain consistent with the
200 magnitude–distance domain relevant for hazard assessment at the storage site
201 (hypocentral distances ≤ 80 km in simulations). The storage reservoir is located at
202 approximately 2.5 to 2.7 km tvdss (true vertical depth subsea), as documented in the
203 approved storage permit. Since the water depth in the Prinos area is ~ 30 m, the depth
204 below seabed is ~ 2.5 to 3.0 km, and any injection-induced events would be expected near

205 reservoir depth or within the upper crustal volume affected by pressure diffusion. Thus,
206 a conservative upper bound of 7 km was adopted to ensure inclusion of events
207 representative of shallow crustal conditions while excluding deeper tectonic earthquakes
208 governed by different stress regimes.

209 Using the *stream2segment* software package (Zaccarelli et al., 2019), we retrieved station
210 xml and raw waveforms for these events as recorded by permanent seismic networks of
211 weak and strong motion data (Evangelidis et al., 2021, see *Data and Resources* for
212 network operators). The waveforms were corrected for mean and trend, filtered from 0.1
213 to 40 Hz (with a fourth-order Butterworth filter) and the instrument response was
214 removed followed by a tapering with a 5%-cosine window. Events were further screened
215 by signal-to-noise ratio (SNR), retaining only spectral values with an SNR larger than 3, to
216 ensure that only those yielding reliable spectral estimates were included. The remaining
217 events form a homogeneous and internally consistent catalogue produced through
218 standard waveform processing, instrument correction and manual quality control. The
219 catalogue information contains all the metadata such as station locations and hypocenter
220 parameters of these 54 events. For compatibility with existing GMMs available for
221 induced seismicity, which are generally based on moment magnitude M_w , instrumentally
222 measured local magnitude M_L values were converted to M_w using equation (1) proposed
223 by Konstantinou and Melis (2018, their region 1) which was later confirmed by
224 Fountoulakis et al. (2023)

225

$$226 \quad M_w = (0.964 \pm 0.021)M_L + (0.147 \pm 0.584) . \quad (1)$$

227

228 Although values for M_w closely approximate M_L values, it must be kept in mind that the
229 scaling of moment magnitudes from local magnitudes will introduce additional
230 uncertainties in the derivation of the GMM, especially at low magnitudes ([Edwards et al.,](#)
231 [2010](#); [Walling et al., 2021](#)). The influence on the derived GMM will be discussed in more
232 detail later. Although this legacy dataset covers the distance range of interest and
233 includes events with adequate signal quality, the magnitude distribution is limited when
234 considered in the context of regression for a hybrid ground-motion model.

235 To broaden the empirical constraints while maintaining a clear separation between
236 calibration of the seismological model and regression for obtaining a GMM, we extended
237 the dataset with additional events identified from continuous waveform data between
238 January 2008 and August 2025. Continuous records from 59 seismic stations within
239 150 km of the Prinos storage site (40.85° N, 24.48° E) were analyzed using a machine
240 learning-based detection and association workflow. Automatic phase identification was
241 performed using the deep-learning picker PhaseNet ([Zhu and Beroza, 2019](#)), employing
242 the model trained on seismic data from the Northern California Seismic Network.
243 Probability thresholds of 0.3 were adopted for both *P*- and *S*-phase identification. The
244 resulting phase picks were associated using the GaMMA algorithm ([Zhu et al., 2022](#)), an
245 unsupervised earthquake associator based on a Gaussian Mixture Model. For the
246 association stage we adopted the Bayesian implementation of GaMMA with an
247 oversampling factor of four and required a minimum of six identified phases (*P* or *S*) for
248 an event to be classified as an earthquake.

249 Event locations were initially determined using a regional one-dimensional velocity model
250 applicable to the area and derived independently from travel-time inversion ([Karabulut](#)
251 [et al., 2006](#)). To capture all earthquakes potentially affecting the storage site, only events
252 located within a spatial window extending approximately 100 km around the area of
253 interest (39.80°–41.80° N, 23.28°–25.67° E) were retained. To improve location accuracy,
254 all associated events were subsequently relocated with NonLinLoc applying source-
255 specific station term (SSST) corrections ([Lomax and Savvaidis, 2022](#)). The relocation used
256 the same velocity model as in the association stage and an Octree search within a volume
257 of 200 km × 265 km × 41 km centered on the Prinos area, allowing the full station
258 geometry and topography to be considered. Quality-control criteria were applied to
259 retain only well-constrained hypocenters: azimuthal gap $\leq 300^\circ$, average RMS residual \leq
260 0.5 s, and major error-ellipsoid semi-axis ≤ 5 km. After this filtering stage, the SSST
261 catalogue consisted of 18,908 well-located earthquakes.

262 To further improve relative location accuracy, the SSST catalogue was processed using the
263 double-difference relocation algorithm HypoDD ([Waldhauser and Ellsworth, 2000](#)).
264 Differential travel-time differences were computed from the automatically detected
265 phase picks for nearby event pairs recorded at the same station. The inversion was
266 performed using the LSQR solver with a minimum of eight differential times per event
267 pair and a damping parameter between 80 and 90 to ensure a stable solution. Out of the
268 initial SSST catalogue, 15,478 events (81.9%) were successfully relocated. From this
269 catalogue, 416 events with focal depths $h \leq 7$ km were retained for further analysis,

270 consistent with the shallow crustal depth range relevant for potential injection-related
271 seismicity at the Prinos reservoir.

272 Waveforms for these events were subsequently extracted and processed for spectral
273 analysis. During this stage, events were screened based on signal-to-noise ratio and
274 waveform quality to ensure that reliable spectral amplitudes could be obtained. Events
275 recorded by too few stations or exhibiting insufficient signal quality were excluded. After
276 this screening, 276 earthquakes with $h \leq 7$ km and adequate signal quality remained and
277 were used in the regression analysis. Magnitudes for the machine learning catalogue were
278 obtained from amplitude measurements associated with the PhaseNet picks and were
279 calibrated against the manually revised catalogue of the National Observatory of Athens
280 (NOA) through a quadratic regression model (see **Supplementary Figure S7**). Residual
281 scatter in the magnitude conversion is not explicitly modelled but may contribute
282 modestly to the between-event variability as discussed below. The resulting catalogue
283 therefore combines automated detection with strict quality control and magnitude
284 calibration against the manually revised NOA catalogue.

285

286 **Figure 2:** Epicentral distribution of the shallow ($h \leq 7$ km) events used in the study that
 287 occurred within a radius of 50 km around the Prinos storage complex (grey-shaded
 288 polyline in the central northern part of the map). Circles with dark color denote the 54
 289 manually reviewed shallow earthquakes, with magnitudes ranging from 0.6 to 3.5,
 290 forming the calibration dataset, alongside the corresponding station locations (squares).
 291 Light circles denote the 276 shallow, machine learning-derived events, with magnitudes
 292 ranging from 1.0 to 3.0, satisfying the relocation and quality criteria described in the text.
 293 Faults lines are as in Figure 1. The color version of this figure is available only in the
 294 electronic edition.

295 Alt text: Topographical map of northern Greece and neighboring countries showing the
 296 spatial distribution of recorded events used for calibration and regression and the spatial
 297 distribution of seismic stations.

298

299 The unified observational dataset (**Figure 2**) therefore consists of two components: the
 300 54 manually reviewed events and an extended set of 276 machine learning-derived
 301 events. In the subsequent calibration of the stochastic model parameters, only the
 302 manually reviewed events are used. During the regression stage, both datasets are

303 incorporated. Here, as previously stated, the contribution of small-magnitude events with
304 few recordings is moderated through a weighting scheme that limits their influence on
305 the hybrid GMM coefficients.

306

307

308 **STOCHASTIC MODELLING OF GROUND MOTION**

309 Conventional GMMs are commonly derived through the non-linear regression of strong
310 motion data recorded within a specific region. This empirical approach is effective when
311 dense datasets are available, but it becomes problematic in regions with sparse seismic
312 observations. Bearing this in mind, predicting ground motion for induced seismicity in our
313 area of interest is challenging. While empirical GMMs are often relatively simple and easy
314 to use, they do have limitations when extrapolated beyond their range of observed data.
315 For induced seismicity, such extrapolation introduces significant epistemic uncertainty,
316 particularly where physical corrections for source or path effects cannot be reliably
317 constrained.

318 In contrast, GMMs supported by physics-based simulations offer greater flexibility. These
319 models are directly tied to the physical processes that control earthquake shaking and
320 can therefore be updated more easily to reflect changes in source, path, or site conditions
321 ([Drouet and Cotton, 2015](#); [Baltay et al., 2017](#)). To this regard, stochastic simulations have
322 become a standard approach to generate ground motions for a given earthquake
323 magnitude and distance utilizing a physical model of source, path and site effects. Various
324 implementations exist in the literature, ranging from source-based models that follow a

325 seismological approach like physics-guided point-source modelling (e.g., Boore, 2003) and
326 finite fault modelling (Boore, 2009) to site-based models (e.g., Rezaeian and Der
327 Kiureghian, 2008; Yamamoto and Baker 2013; Sharbati et al., 2018). In this study, we
328 adopt the stationary stochastic method implemented in the SMSIM code as the baseline
329 simulation tool (Boore, 2003, 2005). In this framework, Fourier amplitude spectra,
330 derived from a seismological model of the source, propagation path, and local site effects,
331 are combined with random phase angles to generate ground motion time series (Boore,
332 2003; Lam, 2023). The approach uses a point-source representation with empirical
333 adjustments to approximate near-source saturation and finite-fault scaling. It has been
334 benchmarked against finite-fault simulations indicating that point-source models can
335 reproduce many key features of ground motions from larger earthquakes (Boore, 2009).
336 Although the rupture geometry is not explicitly modeled, source finiteness is implicitly
337 represented through magnitude-dependent source scaling. Furthermore, SMSIM has
338 been shown to remain stable for small-magnitude crustal events when the key frequency
339 parameters $\Delta\sigma$ and κ_0 are properly constrained (Edwards and Fäh, 2013; Drouet and
340 Cotton, 2015).

341

342 *Description of the model and preliminary model input parameters*

343 The stochastic model's flexibility lies in its capacity that the acceleration Fourier spectrum
344 A_{ij} for an earthquake i at site j can be decomposed into a product of source E , path P , and
345 site S parameters, i.e.

346

347
$$A_{ij}(r_{ij}, f) = E_i(M_{0i}, f) \times P(r_{ij}, f) \times S_j(f) . \quad (2)$$

348

349 All components of equation (2) depend on frequency f and r_{ij} represents the distance
350 between i and j . The description of the source is based on Brune's source model (Brune,
351 1970, 1971) with the seismic moment M_0 . Using the classical description of Brune's
352 model, the seismic moment is mainly controlled by the stress drop and the corner
353 frequency as well as multiplicative correction factors to account for the radiation pattern,
354 amplification due to the free surface as well as the partitioning of energy into the two
355 horizontal components (taken as $1/\sqrt{2}$). Previous studies focusing on the area of interest
356 (Margaris and Boore, 1998; Margaris and Hatzidimitriou, 2002; Grendas et al., 2021, 2022)
357 consistently report a relatively low to moderate stress parameter regime with slightly
358 increasing values from ~ 6 to ~ 55 bars for $2.5 \leq M_w \leq 5.2$. Significantly higher values are
359 only found for reverse faulting mechanisms, but these mechanisms have not been
360 reported in the region of interest. No correlation between the computed stress
361 parameter with respect to the corresponding focal depth is further documented. While
362 we adopted an initial wide range for stress parameter (**Table 1**) to capture inherent
363 epistemic uncertainty, the calibration converged towards a moderate stress drop regime
364 consistent with previous studies.

365 The frequency-dependent decay of P involves anelastic attenuation modelled as
366 $e^{-\pi f (\frac{r_{ij}}{v_s Q(f)})}$ and geometrical spreading. Herein, the frequency-dependent quality factor is
367 modelled as $Q(f) = Q_0 f^\eta$, with η being the exponent accounting for the frequency-
368 dependence of Q . v_s represents the ray path-crustal velocity. For the geometrical

369 spreading, [Bindi et al. \(2023\)](#) suggested a trilinear geometrical spreading with different
370 attenuation rates for short and moderate distances. For the quality factor Q both [Grendas](#)
371 [et al. \(2021\)](#) and [Bindi et al. \(2023\)](#) found relatively moderate anelastic and scattering
372 attenuation in this area.

373 Ground motion simulations also require the inclusion of a path duration function to
374 accurately model the temporal characteristics of seismic wave propagation. This function
375 is commonly parameterized by the significant duration, defined as the time interval
376 required to capture a specified percentage (usually 5% to 75% or 5% to 95% of the total
377 energy) dissipated within the ground motion record. As demonstrated by [Edwards and](#)
378 [Fäh \(2013\)](#) and [Bora et al. \(2014\)](#), the duration of the stochastically simulated data using
379 SMSIM falls between the two aforementioned measures. For reducing complexity, for the
380 path duration we adopt the model of [Bommer et al. \(2016\)](#) and [Suroyo et al. \(2024\)](#) since
381 all regions share similar magnitude, depth and distance and velocity ranges.

382 S is the site effect for station j which we account for by first considering the response at
383 the reference rock level ($v_{S30} = 760$ m/s) followed by applying site-specific amplification
384 factors based on the travel-time based average S -wave velocity in the uppermost 30 m
385 (v_{S30}) and the site-specific high frequency attenuation parameter K_0 ([Anderson and](#)
386 [Hough, 1984](#)). The reference ground motions are then moved to the surface by a
387 convolution with local site amplification factors based on the model of [Boore et al. \(2014\)](#).
388 This model decomposes site response into linear and non-linear components with the
389 former scaling logarithmically with v_{S30} relative to the reference velocity of 760 m/s. For
390 v_{S30} , we rely on the values by [Tani et al. \(2025\)](#) who provide measured values of v_{S30} for

391 more than 300 sites in Greece. The non-linear term depends on reference rock PGA and
392 additional model coefficients provided by [Boore et al. \(2014\)](#).

393 An overview of the parameters of the starting model used for the SMSIM simulations are
394 given in **Table 1**. The first run of SMSIM simulations for the calibration of the stochastic
395 model parameters was performed for moment magnitudes from 0.5 to 4.5, using 0.1-unit
396 steps. As there is clear evidence of predominant strike-slip focal mechanisms in the region
397 of interest, a fictitious similar focal mechanism is assigned based on [Koukouvelas and](#)
398 [Aydin \(2002\)](#).

399

400 *Calibration with real data from Greece*

401 A statistical comparison of the predictions from the stochastic model with real data from
402 the database described above and refinement of the modelling parameters (the
403 frequency-dependent quality factor defined by Q_0 and η , the high-frequency attenuation
404 parameter κ_0 and the stress parameter $\Delta\sigma$) are performed to ensure that simulated
405 ground motions are statistically consistent with observed ground motion data. The
406 geometrical spreading model is not re-calibrated as the values provided in **Table 1** are
407 robust and consistent among the references provided and can be considered sufficiently
408 well constrained.

409 For the calibration, we rely on the basic framework described by [Suroyo et al. \(2024\)](#)
410 which should be referred to for further details. The qualitative assessment of the
411 individual simulations is based on the area metric (AM, described in detail by [Sunny et al.](#)
412 [2022](#)) values which are calculated for both modelled and recorded data by considering

413 the respective spectral distribution as a cumulative distribution function (CDF). The CDF
414 provides the probability that the random variable X takes a value less than or equal to x ,
415 i.e., $CDF(x) = P(X \leq x)$. The AM represents a measure of the discrepancy between the
416 observed and modelled CDFs and it is defined as the integral of the absolute difference
417 between the observed CDF and the modelled CDF. The aim is to refine the seismological
418 model by minimizing the difference between modelled and observed ground motions
419 from past earthquakes.

420 Hereunto, in a first run, we generate a subset of 2,000 parameter combinations of Q_0 , η ,
421 κ_0 and $\Delta\sigma$ with each parameter being sampled independently and according to the
422 parameter ranges listed in **Table 1**. For all parameters, a uniform distribution was used,
423 i.e., each value in the distribution is considered equally probable with the minimum and
424 maximum values being decided based on the site-specific/region-specific information
425 available from the references listed in **Table 1**. Stochastic ground motion simulations are
426 then carried out for each combination of input parameters. We adopted a uniform
427 distribution due to the limited site-specific/region-specific information as well as due to
428 hampered information about the parameter uncertainty; the latter also reflects a lack of
429 reliable prior knowledge about their probability distribution.

430 For a first comparison, we focus on the comparison of peak ground acceleration (PGA)
431 values only. Of the subset of the 2,000 simulations, we retain only those combinations of
432 parameters if the CDF of the simulated ground motions lies within the 95%-confidence
433 interval of the empirical CDF (i.e., the CDF from the recorded data). This includes a subset
434 of 36 parameter combinations. By considering the statistical correlation of the

435 parameters using covariate resampling ([Greenland, 1980](#)), this optimal parameter subset
436 of 36 parameter combinations is increased to 500 correlated parameter subsets.
437 Increasing the number of subsets will enable a better representation of the parameter
438 space consistent with real-world ground motion characteristics. We then use these 500
439 correlated parameters sets as input for the second calibration trial.

440 The latter is based on a different response spectral period (here: $T = 0.5$ s). Hereunto, like
441 [Suroyo et al. \(2024\)](#), a second run is then performed with an identical procedure as
442 described above. Again, we only retain those parameter combinations that fall within the
443 95%-confidence bounds. With this subset, we simulate additional spectral periods
444 ($T = 0.05, 0.2, 1, 2,$ and 5 s). This step provides a subset of 26 parameter combinations. A
445 final filtering step identifies only those common samples from the retained parameter 26
446 combinations that consistently fall within the 95%-confidence intervals at all simulated
447 spectral periods. This ultimately comprises five parameter subsets (**Table 2**) which can be
448 regarded as representing the epistemic parametric uncertainty of our model as described
449 by [Liou and Abrahamson \(2025\)](#). In other words, this subset represents the parameter set
450 consistent with observed data within epistemic bounds, and it can provide a robust basis
451 for seismic hazard and uncertainty analysis over the entire spectral range. The model with
452 the minimum misfit (first column in **Table 2**, $AM = 0.81$) is the final selected “best-
453 estimate” model for the given range of magnitudes and distances. Please note that there
454 is no single “best-estimate” for each of the four parameters, but the minimum misfit is
455 obtained for the combinations of all parameters. As can be seen from **Table 2**, all five
456 combined models are well within the originally defined parameter ranges of **Table 1**.

457

458

459 **Figure 3:** Comparison of SMSIM modelled response spectral accelerations for earthquake
460 magnitudes M2 (black), M4 (red) and M6 (green) at two representative distances of (a)
461 5 km and (b) 30 km. Thick lines show the best-estimate parameter set while dashed lines
462 show the results for the remaining four acceptable parameter subsets listed in **Table 2**.
463 The color version of this figure is available only in the electronic edition.

464 Alt text: Line graphs showing the modelled peak ground acceleration spectra for three
465 different earthquake magnitudes against two hypocentral distances indicating a good
466 agreement over the entire magnitude and distance range.

467

468 Based on the five best-parameter subsets, further simulations are performed for moment
469 magnitudes between 2 and 6 with 0.1-unit steps and distances up to 80 km. **Figure 3**
470 exemplarily shows the simulated response spectral accelerations against two selected
471 hypocentral distances (5 km and 30 km) for various magnitudes. The individual
472 simulations with the five parameter subsets agree well over the entire range of periods
473 and magnitudes with the best-estimate model usually centered between all five
474 parameter models. All subsequent simulations of synthetic data carried out in the
475 following will be based on this best-estimate calibrated parameter model.

476

477

478 **EXISTING GMMs FOR INDUCED SEISMICITY**

479 Although the modelling parameters have been constrained comprehensively, the
480 inherent variability of ground motion data poses challenges for developing and validating
481 robust region-specific GMMs. Prior to introducing a new GMM, a comparison with
482 existing models was conducted to facilitate the selection of a suitable backbone curve.
483 For this purpose, **Table 3** summarizes a selection of representative GMMs for different
484 induced seismicity sites in Europe and worldwide, alongside their respective magnitude
485 and distance applicability ranges. The GMMs were chosen to provide adequate sampling
486 of the parameter space defined by magnitude, distance, and depth, ensuring a
487 comparable distribution of values across these ranges. [Atkinson \(2015\)](#) developed a GMM
488 for small-to-moderate earthquakes ($3 \leq M \leq 6$) at short hypocentral distances (< 40 km)
489 based on a subset of the NGA-West2 database ([Ancheta et al., 2014](#)), thus addressing
490 limitations of standard GMMs calibrated for larger events. [Bommer et al. \(2022\)](#)
491 presented a GMM specifically for induced seismicity adjusted to local site conditions at
492 the Groningen gas field. Unlike standard GMMs, it also accounts for nonlinear site effects
493 and regional differences. The GMM of [Douglas et al. \(2013\)](#) is based on a generic
494 stochastic model suitable for shallow earthquakes with magnitudes ranging from 1 to 5.5
495 at short source-to-site distances. They generated several tens of GMMs to encompass
496 various stress drop and attenuation scenarios. More recently, [Suroyo et al. \(2024\)](#)
497 presented a physically-adjusted GMM for induced seismicity at the Preston New Road
498 shale gas site in the UK. By combining an empirical model with site-specific stochastic
499 simulations, they could improve accuracy despite data scarcity and near-surface

500 heterogeneity. [Yenier et al. \(2017\)](#) adapted a generic GMM, originally developed for
 501 central and eastern North America (CENA) to better account for induced earthquakes in
 502 Oklahoma. Their model showed that large, induced earthquakes ($M \geq 5$) exhibited stress
 503 drop levels comparable to those of natural (tectonic) CENA events.
 504

505

506 **Figure 4:** Modelled spectral intensities (top: PGA for moment magnitudes M2.5 (a) and
 507 M3.0 (b), PSA at $T = 0.2$ s (c) and PSA at $T = 0.5$ s (d) for moment magnitude M2.5) against
 508 hypocentral distance and comparison with various GMMs: [Atkinson \(2015, solid line\)](#),
 509 [Bommer et al. \(2022, dashed line\)](#), [Douglas et al. \(2013, dotted line\)](#), [Suroyo et al. \(2024,](#)
 510 [loosely dashed line\)](#) and [Yenier et al. \(2017, dashed-dotted line\)](#). Synthetic (black circles)
 511 and recorded (black triangles) data with magnitude values ± 0.2 given in each plot are
 512 overlain.

513 Alt text: Line graphs showing the modelled and recorded spectral intensities for two
 514 different magnitudes and for different spectral periods against hypocentral distance
 515 indicating varying levels of agreement with various existing GMMs for induced seismicity.
 516

517

518 **Figure 4** provides a comparison of the region-specific data for the Prinos site and the
519 respective ground motion models across different spectral periods. Observed and
520 simulated spectral intensities for events within ± 0.2 magnitude units are plotted on top
521 using the best-estimate calibrated parameter model. There are no recordings available at
522 very short distances, while at larger distances, the simulations generally reproduce well
523 the spectral intensities observed in the recordings.

524 Among the multiple empirical models proposed by [Douglas et al. \(2013\)](#), we only use here
525 their “model 1” because the values for the stress drop and attenuation parameters are
526 closest to the calibrated parameters of the best-estimate model listed in **Table 3** (i.e.,
527 their model with $\Delta\sigma = 10$ bar, $Q_0 = 200$, $\kappa_0 = 0.04$ s). This model, however, shows rather
528 poor predictions for both PGA and 5%-damped pseudo-spectral acceleration (PSA) within
529 its valid magnitude and distance range. The model by [Bommer et al. \(2022\)](#) incorporates
530 several region-specific factors to reflect the specific site response characteristics of the
531 thick soil deposits of the Groningen gas field and it is therefore difficult to be applied in a
532 more general framework. By contrast, the model of [Atkinson \(2015\)](#) and its subsequent
533 update by [Yenier et al. \(2017\)](#), provide satisfactory predictions over the full distance
534 range, even when applied below their original magnitude range. The base model of
535 [Suroyo et al. \(2024\)](#) builds upon this approach and shows similar good performance.

536 The calibration of Q_0 , η , κ_0 and $\Delta\sigma$ relies exclusively on the homogeneous 54-event
537 dataset and yields a physically consistent parameter space for the stochastic simulations.
538 Once these calibrated parameters are fixed, the regression stage of the hybrid model
539 incorporates both the original 54 events and the additional 276 machine learning-derived

540 events. This separation ensures that the stochastic model is anchored by a uniform and
541 controlled dataset, while the hybrid regression fully exploits the extended observational
542 database to stabilise the median trends and variability terms of the model.

543

544

545 **HYBRID GROUND MOTION MODEL**

546 The hybrid ground-motion model combines calibrated stochastic simulations with
547 empirical observations using a one-stage mixed-effects regression following the standard
548 formulation of [Abrahamson and Youngs, 1992](#) and [Joyner and Boore \(1993\)](#). For each
549 observation $\log Y_{ij}$ from earthquake i recorded at station j , the model is decomposed as

550

$$551 \quad \log Y_{ij} = f(M_i, r_{ij}, c) + \delta B_i + \delta W_{ij} \quad (3)$$

552

553 where $f(M_i, r_{ij}, c)$, as discussed later following equation (5), represents the fixed-effects
554 functional form for capturing the scaling of PSA with magnitude and distance.

555 $\delta B_i \sim N(0, \tau^2)$ is the between-event random effect capturing systematic deviations
556 attributable to source characteristics of individual earthquakes. Herein, τ is the between-
557 event variability. $\delta W_{ij} \sim N(0, \phi^2)$ is the within-event residual accounting for station-to-
558 station variability ϕ for recordings from the same event. The two random effects are
559 assumed mutually independent, so that the total variability is $\sigma^2 = \tau^2 + \phi^2$.

560 For the n_i observations from event i , the vector of residuals $r_i = \log Y_{ij} - f(M_i, r_{ij}, c)$

561 follows a multivariate normal distribution with the compound-symmetry covariance

562 matrix $\Sigma_i = \tau^2 \mathbf{1}_{n_i} \mathbf{1}_{n_i}^T + \phi^2 \mathbf{I}_{n_i}$ with \mathbf{I} being the identity matrix. The full restricted log-
563 likelihood is therefore

564

$$565 \quad \log(l_R(\tau, \phi)) = -\frac{1}{2} \sum_i [\log|\Sigma_i| + r_i^T \Sigma_i^{-1} r_i + (n_i - 2) \log(2\pi)] \quad (4)$$

566

567 We rely on the Restricted Maximum Likelihood (REML) rather than the full ML because
568 REML integrates out the fixed effects before maximizing the likelihood with respect to the
569 variance components, thereby yielding unbiased estimates of τ and ϕ regardless of the
570 number of fixed-effects parameters (Bates et al., 2015). The optimization is performed
571 using the BOBYQA (Bound Optimization BY Quadratic Approximation) algorithm, as
572 implemented in the lme4 package in R (Bates et al., 2015). Convergence is declared when
573 two conditions are jointly satisfied: the relative change in the REML criterion between
574 successive iterations falls below 10^{-6} , and the norm of the scaled gradient vector is less
575 than 10^{-3} . No convergence warnings were issued for any of the spectral periods reported
576 in Table 4 of the manuscript.

577 After calibrating the parameters of the seismological model, the hybrid GMM regression
578 incorporates the recordings from both the calibration dataset and the 276 additional
579 machine learning-derived events. Although the machine learning-catalogue substantially
580 improves the magnitude-distance sampling of the observational dataset, the distribution
581 of the automatically detected events is strongly skewed toward the lower magnitude
582 range (see **Supplementary Figures S4 and S5**). Several of the smallest events are recorded
583 by only one or two stations, even after the application of the SNR threshold and location-

584 quality filters described above. The imbalance in the number of records per event
585 introduces a natural dominance of small-magnitude, sparsely recorded events during
586 regression. To avoid introducing a downward bias in the predicted intensity measures
587 affecting the hybrid ground-motion model, all waveforms are weighted by the number of
588 observations for each event. This procedure ensures that events with limited
589 observational support do not disproportionately influence the median prediction or the
590 variability terms while it preserves the spectral information content, especially at short
591 distances. This weighting is also applied solely to the fixed-effects portion of the mixed-
592 effects model while the random effects, representing the corresponding variabilities, are
593 estimated separately and are not affected by this weighting ensuring that natural
594 variability is preserved. This approach improves the fit of the fixed-effects terms without
595 artificially reducing the variability captured by the random effects ([Abrahamson and](#)
596 [Youngs, 1992](#)). All observed ground motions are harmonized to M_w and combined with
597 the stochastic simulations, thereby ensuring that the resulting hybrid model reflects both
598 the physical constraints of the calibrated source-path properties and the empirical
599 strength of the combined observational dataset.

600 [Bommer et al. \(2006\)](#) and [Atkinson \(2008\)](#) have shown that improvements in local ground
601 motion modelling can be achieved using the referenced empirical approach, i.e. the
602 functional form of an underlying base GMM is calibrated to ground motions in the region
603 of interest. Based on the model comparisons described in the previous section, our model
604 is based on the functional form presented by [Atkinson \(2015\)](#) and [Yenier et al. \(2017\)](#).
605 This model accounts for the source and geometrical attenuation effects and is written as

606

$$\log Y = c_0 + c_1 \mathbf{M} + c_2 \mathbf{M}^2 + F(R) . \quad (5)$$

608

609 Herein, the logs are in base10. Y corresponds to the ground motion parameter and \mathbf{M} is
610 moment magnitude. $F(R)$ is the geometrical spreading classified into two distance
611 segments

612

$$F(R) = \begin{cases} c_{3a} \log(R) & R \leq 12\text{km} \\ c_{3a} \log(12) + c_{3b} \log(R/12) & R > 12\text{km} \end{cases} \quad (6)$$

614

615 R corresponds to the effective distance which causes the near-distance saturation,
616 meaning that the attenuation curve will approach a constant value for decreasing rupture
617 distances since at any point one cannot be close to the entire fault plane (Joyner and
618 Boore, 1981). Obviously, R is magnitude-dependent and takes larger values for increasing
619 magnitudes. Atkinson (2015) proposed two models for R of which we have chosen

620

$$R = \sqrt{r_{hypo}^2 + \max(1, 10^{-0.28+0.19\mathbf{M}})^2} . \quad (7)$$

622

623 Equation (7) corresponds to a magnitude-dependent pseudo-fault dimension consistent
624 with subsequent studies (Atkinson et al., 2016; Atkinson, 2020). r_{hypo} in equation (7)
625 corresponds to the hypocentral distance. The model, as described by equation (5),
626 calculates spectral amplitudes increasing nonlinearly with earthquake magnitude. The

627 inclusion of a quadratic term for magnitude ensures that this increase is not constant as
628 larger events generally produce disproportionately larger ground motions. The functional
629 form, however, does not include a hinge magnitude as this is required only for the upper
630 magnitude scaling.

631 The regression coefficients in equations (5) and (6), together with their associated inter-
632 and intra-event residuals, are then obtained through a nonlinear mixed-effects regression
633 technique (i.e., combining the deterministic part of the GMM and random effects to
634 address the variability unexplained by the fixed effects). The inter- and intra-event
635 components of the total variability σ represent the event-to-event variability (τ) as well
636 as the variability between observations of a single event (φ). Synthetic data were
637 generated for magnitudes $2 \leq M_w \leq 6$ at distances up to 80 km using SMSIM simulations
638 based on a strike-slip focal mechanism and the best-estimate model described above. In
639 the final regression presented in **Table 4**, simulated and observed datasets are
640 incorporated with equal weight, while additional sensitivity tests using reduced weights
641 for simulated data produced only minor variations in scaling coefficients but somewhat
642 larger within-event variability (see **Supplementary Table S1**).

643 Within-event variability (φ) is slightly larger than the between-event variability (τ) for the
644 Prinos dataset, consistent with observations in other induced seismicity contexts (e.g.,
645 [Bommer and Stafford, 2020](#) among others). However, the decrease of τ at longer spectral
646 periods might imply that the spectral ordinates at these periods are increasingly
647 controlled by the low-frequency components of the source spectrum. This behavior could
648 indicate a smoothing or masking of variability in parameters like stress drop. While not

649 negligible, variability in the focal mechanism orientation and its mapping onto the
650 radiation pattern is expected to remain a significant contributor even at intermediate-to-
651 long periods.

652

653

654 **DISCUSSION**

655 **Figure 5** shows residuals between observed (both the original 54 events and the
656 additional 276 machine learning-derived) and simulated ground motions relative to the
657 predictions from the hybrid ground motion model (**Table 4**), expressed as \log_{10}
658 differences. No systematic trends are evident across the spectral range except for an
659 underprediction at very small magnitudes for small spectral periods. Longer spectral
660 periods at very small magnitudes, on the other hand, show a slight overprediction. These
661 deviations cannot be attributed to the near-source term in equation (7) which has
662 negligible effects for $M \leq 2$ events. For the smallest magnitudes (this largely encompasses
663 machine learning-derived events), the scatter is relatively large (standard deviation
664 corresponding to a factor of ~ 3). Hereunto, to assess the influence of these machine
665 learning-derived events on the hybrid GMM, we performed a sensitivity analysis by re-
666 estimating the regression model after excluding these events. The values are shown in
667 **Supplementary Table S2**. While changes in the magnitude and distance scaling
668 coefficients are minor, the between-event variability slightly decreases ($< 10\%$) as
669 contributors to the between-event scatter (e.g. stress drop scaling) are removed. The
670 decrease for the within-variability is larger and in the order of 20% . Small-magnitude

671 events typically exhibit higher within-event variability as local site conditions and path
672 heterogeneity have a proportionally larger impact on their weaker motions.

673 The question arises as to whether some of these deviations can be attributed to the use
674 of simulations and/or tectonic earthquakes for the calibration of a model intended for
675 induced seismicity. Such an approach will inevitably introduce epistemic uncertainties.
676 For example, while several studies report broadly comparable stress drop scaling
677 between tectonic and induced earthquakes (e.g., [Justinic et al., 2013](#); [Huang et al., 2016](#),
678 [2017](#); [Fan and McGuire, 2018](#); [Wu et al., 2018](#); [Yoshimitsu et al., 2019](#); [Jeong et al., 2021](#)),
679 other studies report systematically lower stress drop values and non-constant scaling for
680 injection-induced earthquakes (e.g., [Fehler and Phillips, 1991](#); [Abercrombie and Leary,](#)
681 [1993](#); [Goertz-Allmann et al., 2011](#); [Hough, 2014, 2015](#); [Sumy et al., 2017](#); [Trugman et al.,](#)
682 [2017](#); [Chen and Abercrombie, 2020](#); [Jeong et al., 2022](#); [Eulenfeld et al., 2023](#); [Shen et al.,](#)
683 [2023](#); [Jeong and Liu, 2025](#)). In the absence of local recording of induced seismicity,
684 adopting stress-drop values derived from shallow tectonic earthquakes represents a
685 pragmatic working assumption.

686

687 **Figure 5:** Residuals (\log_{10} scale), i.e., recorded (crosses, both the original 54 events and
 688 the additional 276 machine learning-derived) and modelled (circles) minus predicted PGA
 689 (a,b) and PSA at $T = 0.5$ s (c,d) using the newly derived hybrid GMM shown versus moment
 690 magnitude (a,c) and hypocentral distance (b,d). Modelling was carried out on 0.1-
 691 magnitude and 2.5 km distance grid. Mean and standard deviations for various magnitude
 692 and distance bins are also shown (herein, each magnitude bin corresponds to one unit of
 693 magnitude, and each distance bin corresponds to 20 km).

694 Alt text: Residuals of the newly derived hybrid GMM for two different spectral periods
 695 indicating no significant under- or overprediction of the entire magnitude and distance
 696 ranges.

697

698

699 In this study, however, this equivalence is not assumed generically but under specific
 700 physical conditions. The storage reservoir is located at approximately 2.5 to 2.7 km depth,

701 and injection-related seismicity would therefore be expected within the shallow crustal

702 volume affected by pressure perturbations in the vicinity of the reservoir interval. The

703 calibration dataset is therefore restricted to earthquakes with depths ≤ 7 km in order to
704 ensure broadly comparable crustal pressure, temperature, and attenuation conditions.
705 Moreover, induced earthquakes typically occur through the reactivation of pre-existing
706 faults within the prevailing regional stress field rather than through the generation of
707 fundamentally different rupture processes (McGarr 2002). In the Prinos–Kavala region,
708 shallow tectonic seismicity occurs on pre-existing fault structures within the same
709 regional stress regime that would govern injection-related fault reactivation, suggesting
710 that rupture orientation, radiation characteristics, and first-order source scaling are not
711 expected to differ fundamentally. Under these conditions, shallow tectonic earthquakes
712 provide the closest available empirical analogue for the source, path, and attenuation
713 properties expected for potential injection-induced events.

714 Potential differences between tectonic and induced earthquakes would primarily
715 manifest through variations in stress drop and associated corner-frequency scaling. If
716 induced earthquakes were systematically characterized by lower stress drop, near-field
717 high-frequency amplitudes could be overestimated; conversely, higher stress-drop values
718 would result in underestimation of high-frequency motion. However, Huang et al. (2017)
719 showed that, once focal depth and style of the fault are considered, the stress drops of
720 induced and tectonic earthquakes in the central U.S. are statistically similar, indicating
721 that the rupture processes can be comparable under these conditions.

722 In the stochastic simulations, stress drop is therefore treated as an adjustable parameter
723 and calibrated using the shallow-event dataset, while epistemic parametric uncertainty is
724 represented by retaining several acceptable parameter subsets. In addition, the final

725 hybrid GMM integrates empirical observations and simulations through mixed-effects
726 regression, which reduces sensitivity to any single assumption regarding source scaling.
727 This formulation separates between-event and within-event variability and reduces the
728 disproportionate influence of well-recorded earthquakes while still allowing all recordings
729 to contribute to the estimation of path and site scaling but constraining the applicability
730 of the model to shallow, small-to-moderate magnitude events within the calibrated
731 magnitude-distance range.

732 To quantify the influence of the stochastic simulations on the final regression results, we
733 performed an additional analysis in which the simulated data were down-weighted
734 relative to the recorded observations by modifying the diagonal elements of the within-
735 event block of the covariance matrix. The random-effects variance components τ and ϕ
736 are estimated from the unweighted residuals so that the natural aleatory variability of the
737 dataset is preserved ([Abrahamson and Youngs, 1992](#)). The resulting GMM coefficients are
738 provided in **Supplementary Table S2**. Variations for GMM coefficients are small (< 10 %),
739 indicating a robust magnitude and distance scaling. In contrast, the within-event
740 variability increases noticeably, particularly at short periods. We interpret this as an
741 indication that station-to-station scatter, likely related to unresolved site and path effects,
742 becomes more influential when simulations are down-weighted. The between-event
743 variability, however, remains largely unchanged as the recorded earthquakes are not
744 expected to exhibit systematically different event terms. Overall, these findings suggest
745 that the simulations tend to underrepresent the variability associated with path and site
746 effects, in agreement with the conclusions of [Liu et al. \(2025\)](#).

747 To further evaluate the behaviour of the derived model, it is compared with previously
 748 published GMMs. **Figure 6** compares the newly derived hybrid GMM with those already
 749 introduced above (see **Table 3**). The model for the Prinos region reproduces the general
 750 magnitude- and distance-scaling trends of these reference equations. Although the
 751 scatter is large, especially for smaller magnitudes, our model does not take extreme
 752 values and lies in the middle between the other models. For the entire magnitude range,
 753 the overall attenuation pattern remains moderate but consistent with the regional
 754 observations (as can be seen from **Figure 4**).

755

756 **Figure 6:** Predicted PGA values for reference rock conditions ($v_{S30} = 760$ m/s) based on
 757 different GMMs listed in **Table 3** within their applicability ranges: **Atkinson (2015**, solid
 758 lines), **Bommer et al. (2022**, dashed lines), **Douglas et al. (2013**, dotted lines), **Yenier et al.**

759 (2017, dashed-dotted lines) and Suroyo et al. (2024, loosely dashed lines) and our new
760 hybrid GMM model (thick solid lines) for moment magnitudes M2 (black), M3 (green), M4
761 (red) and M5 (blue). The color version of this figure is available only in the electronic
762 edition.

763 Alt text: Line plot showing the level of PGA based on the newly derived hybrid GMM and
764 other existing GMMs for induced seismicity for four different magnitudes indicating the
765 new GMM takes a middle position between the other models but shows a more moderate
766 decay with distance.

767

768 A similar moderate decay pattern has also been observed at North American sites, but it
769 is less pronounced in injection-focused regions such as Preston New Road or Groningen
770 (Atkinson, 2015; Suroyo et al., 2024). Such behavior is physically consistent with the
771 relatively deeper focal depths of tectonic calibration events compared with those for
772 induced events along with moderate stress parameters. Injection-induced events at
773 Prinos, however, occur at relatively deep layers (several kilometers) with respect to other
774 injection sites and may there show similar attenuation characteristics even though
775 uncertainties remain.

776 The calibration of ground motion variability using the SMSIM framework enables a
777 transparent representation of the model's epistemic parametric uncertainty by sampling
778 distinct source-parameter subsets (Douglas et al., 2013). Here, five parameter subsets
779 were retained (Table 2), each reproducing observed and simulated amplitudes within the
780 95% confidence limits of the empirical data. We consider that these subsets define a
781 plausible range of predictions for the magnitude and distance range and provide a formal
782 representation of one component of the epistemic uncertainty in the hybrid model.

783 Uncertainty in magnitude conversion was not incorporated into the variability terms
784 listed in Table 4. Any deviation from the conversion formula (equation 1) could map into

785 the source term of the regression, increasing the event-to-event variability (τ). While the
786 used magnitude conversion is well constrained for moderate magnitudes ($M \geq 3$),
787 uncertainty may be higher for smaller events, especially when extrapolating beyond the
788 magnitude range of the recorded data. The model should therefore be considered semi-
789 empirical with its validity primarily supported by simulation consistency and available
790 observations.

791 So, in the end, what would be the likely effects of some scenario events around the Prinos
792 site? To this regard, we define three earthquake scenarios (from M3.0 to M4.5 at
793 plausible source depths of 3 km having a strike-slip focal mechanism) that can be
794 considered possible and not unlikely as CO₂ injection is expected to happen in this depth
795 range (Koukouzias et al., 2009). We used a deterministic approach and the hybrid GMM
796 to characterize the soil acceleration associated with these three ruptures. In parallel,
797 ground motion is modelled combining GMMs for induced seismicity (**Table 3**) for which
798 we assign an equal weight to each relationship (**Supplementary Figures S8 to S10** show
799 an individual comparison with all GMMs). Distances that account for rupture geometry
800 (Joyner-Boore distance, rupture distance) were measured adopting a circular horizontal
801 rupture centered at the hypocenter with rupture area estimated from the scaling of Wells
802 and Coppersmith (1994). For the latter, the resulting ShakeMaps (**Figure 7**) show PGA
803 contours that decay roughly symmetrically from the epicentral region with peak near-
804 field accelerations ranging from approximately 0.21 to 2.3 m/s² (~ 2 to 24% g) as
805 magnitude increases from 3.0 to 4.5. Comparison of ShakeMaps generated with the
806 hybrid GMM shows slightly lower amplitudes in the near-field for the larger magnitude

807 scenarios while the overall decay is slightly weaker. For the simulated scenarios, only a
808 light level of perceived shaking would be expected in populated areas on land.

809 These scenarios can be considered as illustrative first-order approximations of potential
810 induced events although they do not account for uncertainties of seismicity patterns,
811 style-of faulting, location and seismicity depth-distribution. As discussed in detail in [Baker
812 et al. \(2021\)](#), model uncertainty is generally systematically underestimated when a single
813 simulation approach is used although the modelling results depend more on parameter
814 consistency than on the choice of simulation code ([Omkar et al. 2026](#)). Regarding the
815 development of the hybrid GMM, however, the epistemic variability is partially mitigated
816 through parameter sampling although not all physical processes – such as 3-D wave-
817 propagation effects, offshore path attenuation or site amplification under seafloor
818 conditions – can explicitly be taken into account. Similarly, variability in focal mechanisms
819 can affect scaling coefficients at intermediate to long periods while stress drop variability
820 primarily influences scaling at short periods.

821 Future work should therefore focus on extending the SMSIM-based hybrid model with
822 numerical simulations incorporating basin geometry, offshore sedimentary structure, and
823 bathymetric effects, which may further influence the amplitude and frequency content of
824 ground motions near the Prinos storage site. Finally, while the present model represents
825 a first hybrid and hybrid-calibrated GMM for induced seismicity at a CO₂ storage site in
826 Greece, it can be regarded as a reference framework but it also highlights the need for
827 recalibration should injection-related seismicity be observed in the future.

New GMM

Average of GMMs

829 **Figure 7.** Spatial distribution of PGA around the Prinos CO₂ storage site as predicted by
830 the hybrid GMM developed in this study (*left column*) and by the combination of the
831 GMMs listed in Table 3 (*right column*, equal weights) for reference rock conditions
832 ($V_{S30} = 760$ m/s). Each row corresponds to a different earthquake moment magnitude
833 scenario (M3.0, 4.0 and 4.5). The red star marks the assumed epicenter. Solid isolines
834 correspond to PGA intervals. The color version of this figure is available only in the
835 electronic edition.

836 Alt text: ShakeMaps comparing the spatial distribution of ground motion of the new
837 hybrid GMM and other GMMs indicating a symmetrical decay from the epicentral region
838 with the hybrid GMM showing slightly lower PGA amplitudes in the near-field for the
839 larger magnitude scenarios and a more moderate decay.

840

841

842

843 **CONCLUSIONS**

844 Accurate prediction of ground motions from smaller and more shallow earthquakes –

845 such as those associated with induced seismicity – requires target-specific modelling. We

846 present a new hybrid ground motion model developed and calibrated specifically for the

847 CO₂ sequestration site at Prinos, northern Greece applicable to predict shallow ground

848 motion for magnitudes between $2 \leq M_w \leq 6$ and hypocentral distances up to 80 km. Using

849 well-recorded local waveforms that have occurred in the region of interest, we performed

850 an initial set of ground motion simulations. A quantitative comparison allows subsequent

851 refinement through a calibration process to incorporate region- and event-specific

852 information with the final parameter subset, each of which reproduced ground motions

853 within the 95% confidence band of the empirical data, representing the final model's

854 epistemic parametric uncertainty. The updated complementary simulated motions,

855 combined with observed data enlarged by machine learning-derived events, were then

856 calibrated to a reference GMM to create a hybrid functional form capable of predicting

857 ground motion across a broader range of magnitudes and distances. This newly derived

858 hybrid GMM, informed by both a physical model and stochastic simulations, predicts
859 ground motions consistent with other existing GMMs for induced seismicity at short
860 distances but it exhibits a more moderate spectral decay. The spatial distribution of the
861 levels of ground motion for potential earthquakes has also been visualized. In turn, the
862 hybrid and physically-guided GMM can provide a framework for seismic hazard
863 assessment around the Prinos-Kavala basin supporting the evaluation of the effects on
864 the structural response and risk under potential injection-induced seismicity. The
865 presented framework may also serve as a reference for other CO₂ storage sites in similar
866 tectonic settings while further refinement is possible as additional local seismic data
867 become available.

868 **Declaration of competing interests**

869 The authors acknowledge that there are no conflicts of interest recorded.

870

871

872 **Data and resources**

873 Earthquake parameters for the calibration dataset were retrieved from
874 (<https://bbnet.gein.noa.gr/HL/databases/database>) and the associated waveforms from
875 the ORFEUS EIDA (<https://www.orfeus-eu.org/data/eida/>). We used waveform data from
876 the HL network operated by the Geodynamics Institute of the National Observatory of
877 Athens (NOA) (doi: 10.7914/SN/HL), the HI strong-motion network operated by the
878 Institute of Engineering Seismology and Earthquake Engineering (ITSAK) (doi:
879 10.7914/SN/HI), the HA network operated by the National and Kapodistrian University of
880 Athens (NKUA) (doi: 10.7914/SN/HA), the HT network operated by the Geophysical
881 Laboratory of the Aristotle University of Thessaloniki (AUTH) (doi: 10.7914/SN/HT), the
882 EUROSEISTEST Strong Motion Network (doi: 10.7914/SN/EG) and the 1Y AdriaArray
883 Temporary Network: (doi: 10.7914/y0t2-3b67). Waveform retrieval and metadata
884 handling were carried out using the *stream2segment* software package (Zaccarelli et al.,
885 2019) available at: <https://github.com/rizac/stream2segment>. The SMSIM code is
886 available at https://www.daveboore.com/software_online.html, last accessed October
887 2025. Supplemental Material for this article includes (1) magnitude, distance and depth
888 information of the datasets used for calibration and GMM regression, (2) scenario

889 comparisons of the spatial distribution of PGA around the Prinos CO₂ storage site for three
890 assumed earthquake scenarios and (3) tables showing mixed effect regression results for
891 the coefficients of the GMM and corresponding residuals based on various data sets.

892

893

894

895 **Acknowledgements**

896 The study has been carried out in the framework of the project COREu (CO₂ routes across
897 Europe). This project has received funding from the European Union's HE Research and
898 Innovation Program under grant agreement No. 101136217. The authors thank Iulia
899 Armeanu for her support in the data preparation. Reviews of two anonymous reviewers
900 and comments of associate editor Aybige Akinci are gratefully acknowledged.

901

902

903 **References**

904 Abrahamson, N. A., Youngs, R. R. (1992). A stable algorithm for regression analyses using
905 the random effects model. *Bulletin of the Seismological Society of America*, 82(1), 505-
906 510.

907

908 Ameri, G., Gallovič, F., Pacor, F., Emolo, A. (2009). Uncertainties in strong ground-motion
909 prediction with finite-fault synthetic seismograms: An application to the 1984 M 5.7
910 Gubbio, central Italy, earthquake. *Bulletin of the Seismological Society of America*, 99(2A),
911 647-663.

912

913 Ancheta, T. D., Darragh, R. B., Stewart, J. P., Seyhan, E., Silva, W. J., Chiou, B. S. J., ...
914 Donahue, J. L. (2014). NGA-West2 database. *Earthquake Spectra*, 30(3), 989-1005.

915

916 Anderson, J. G., Hough, S. E. (1984). A model for the shape of the Fourier amplitude
917 spectrum of acceleration at high frequencies. *Bulletin of the Seismological Society of*
918 *America*, 74(5), 1969-1993.

919

920 Arvanitis, A., Koutsovitis, P., Koukoulas, N., Tyrologou, P., Karapanos, D., Karkalis, C.,
921 Pomonis, P. (2020). Potential sites for underground energy and CO2 storage in Greece: A
922 geological and petrological approach. *Energies*, 13(11), 2707.

923

924 Atkinson, G. M. (2008). Ground-motion prediction equations for eastern North America
925 from a referenced empirical approach: Implications for epistemic uncertainty. *Bulletin of*
926 *the Seismological Society of America*, 98(3), 1304-1318.

927

928 Atkinson, G. M. (2015). Ground-motion prediction equation for small-to-moderate events
929 at short hypocentral distances, with application to induced-seismicity hazards. *Bulletin of*
930 *the Seismological Society of America*, 105(2A), 981-992.

931

932 Atkinson, G. M. (2020). The intensity of ground motions from induced earthquakes with
933 implications for damage potential. *Bulletin of the Seismological Society of America*,
934 110(5), 2366-2379.

935

936 Atkinson, G. M., Boore, D. M. (2006). Earthquake ground-motion prediction equations for
937 eastern North America. *Bulletin of the seismological society of America*, 96(6), 2181-2205.

938

939 Atkinson, G. M., Yenier, E., Sharma, N., Convertito, V. (2016). Constraints on the near-
940 distance saturation of ground-motion amplitudes for small-to-moderate induced
941 earthquakes. *Bulletin of the Seismological Society of America*, 106(5), 2104-2111.

942

943 Avraam, G. C., Vatalis, K. I. (2023). A Concise Review of Carbon Dioxide Storage in
944 Depleted Oil Fields of Prinos in Northern Greece. *Materials Proceedings*, 15(1), 18.

945

946 Baker, J., Bradley, B., Stafford, P. (2021). Seismic hazard and risk analysis. Cambridge
947 University Press.

948

949 Baltay, A. S., Hanks, T. C., Abrahamson, N. A. (2017). Uncertainty, variability, and
950 earthquake physics in ground-motion prediction equations. *Bulletin of the Seismological*
951 *Society of America*, 107(4), 1754-1772.

952

953 Bates, D., Mächler, M., Bolker, B., Walker, S. (2015). Fitting linear mixed-effects models
954 using lme4. *Journal of statistical software*, 67, 1-48.

955

956 Bindi, D., Zaccarelli, R., Razafindrakoto, H. N. T., Yen, M. H., Cotton, F. (2023). Empirical
957 shaking scenarios for Europe: a feasibility study. *Geophysical Journal International*,
958 232(2), 990-1005.

959

960 Bommer, J. J., Dost, B., Edwards, B., Stafford, P. J., van Elk, J., Doornhof, D., Ntinalexis, M.
961 (2016). Developing an application-specific ground-motion model for induced seismicity.
962 *Bulletin of the Seismological Society of America*, 106(1), 158-173.
963
964 Bommer, J. J., Douglas, J., Scherbaum, F., Cotton, F., Bungum, H., Fah, D. (2010). On the
965 selection of ground-motion prediction equations for seismic hazard analysis.
966 *Seismological Research Letters*, 81(5), 783-793.
967
968 Bommer, J. J., Oates, S., Cepeda, J. M., Lindholm, C., Bird, J., Torres, R., ... Rivas, J. (2006).
969 Control of hazard due to seismicity induced by a hot fractured rock geothermal project.
970 *Engineering geology*, 83(4), 287-306.
971
972 Bommer, J. J., Stafford, P. J. (2020). Selecting ground-motion models for site-specific
973 PSHA: Adaptability versus applicability. *Bulletin of the Seismological Society of America*,
974 110(6), 2801-2815.
975
976 Bommer, J. J., Stafford, P. J., Ruigrok, E., Rodriguez-Marek, A., Ntinalexis, M., Kruiver, P.
977 P., ... van Elk, J. (2022). Ground-motion prediction models for induced earthquakes in the
978 Groningen gas field, the Netherlands. *Journal of Seismology*, 26(6), 1157-1184.
979
980 Boore, D. M. (2003). Simulation of ground motion using the stochastic method. *Pure and*
981 *applied geophysics*, 160, 635-676.
982
983 Boore, D. M. (2009). Comparing stochastic point-source and finite-source ground-motion
984 simulations: SMSIM and EXSIM. *Bulletin of the Seismological Society of America*, 99(6),
985 3202-3216.
986
987 Boore, D. M., Stewart, J. P., Seyhan, E., Atkinson, G. M. (2014). NGA-West2 equations for
988 predicting PGA, PGV, and 5% damped PSA for shallow crustal earthquakes. *Earthquake*
989 *Spectra*, 30(3), 1057-1085.
990
991 Bora, S. S., Scherbaum, F., Kuehn, N., Stafford, P. (2014). Fourier spectral-and duration
992 models for the generation of response spectra adjustable to different source-,
993 propagation-, and site conditions. *Bulletin of Earthquake Engineering*, 12, 467-493.
994
995 Brune, J. N. (1970). Tectonic stress and the spectra of seismic shear waves from
996 earthquakes. *Journal of geophysical research*, 75(26), 4997-5009.
997
998 Brune, J. N. (1971). Seismic sources, fault plane studies and tectonics. *Eos, Transactions*
999 *American Geophysical Union*, 52(5), IUGG-178.
1000
1001 Chiou, B., Youngs, R., Abrahamson, N., Addo, K. (2010). Ground-motion attenuation
1002 model for small-to-moderate shallow crustal earthquakes in California and its

1003 implications on regionalization of ground-motion prediction models. *Earthquake spectra*,
1004 26(4), 907-926.

1005

1006 Cotton, F., Scherbaum, F., Bommer, J. J., Bungum, H. (2006). Criteria for selecting and
1007 adjusting ground-motion models for specific target regions: Application to central Europe
1008 and rock sites. *Journal of Seismology*, 10, 137-156.

1009

1010 Danciu, L., Nandan, S., Reyes, C. G., Basili, R., Weatherill, G., Beauval, C., ... Giardini, D.
1011 (2021). The 2020 update of the European Seismic Hazard Model-ESHM20: model
1012 overview. *EFHR Technical Report*, 1.

1013

1014 Douglas, J., Edwards, B., Convertito, V., Sharma, N., Tramelli, A., Kraaijpoel, D., ... Troise,
1015 C. (2013). Predicting ground motion from induced earthquakes in geothermal areas.
1016 *Bulletin of the Seismological Society of America*, 103(3), 1875-1897.

1017

1018 Drouet, S., Cotton, F. (2015). Regional stochastic GMPEs in low-seismicity areas: Scaling
1019 and aleatory variability analysis—Application to the French Alps. *Bulletin of the*
1020 *Seismological Society of America*, 105(4), 1883-1902.

1021

1022 Edwards, B., Allmann, B., Fäh, D., Clinton, J. (2010). Automatic computation of moment
1023 magnitudes for small earthquakes and the scaling of local to moment magnitude.
1024 *Geophysical Journal International*, 183(1), 407-420.

1025

1026 Edwards, B., Crowley, H., Pinho, R., Bommer, J. J. (2021). Seismic hazard and risk due to
1027 induced earthquakes at a shale gas site. *Bulletin of the Seismological Society of America*,
1028 111(2), 875-897.

1029

1030 Edwards, B., Douglas, J. (2013). Selecting ground-motion models developed for induced
1031 seismicity in geothermal areas. *Geophysical Journal International*, 195(2), 1314-1322.

1032

1033 Edwards, B., Fäh, D. (2013). A stochastic ground-motion model for Switzerland. *Bulletin*
1034 *of the Seismological Society of America*, 103(1), 78-98.

1035

1036 Edwards, B., Zurek, B., Van Dedem, E., Stafford, P. J., Oates, S., Van Elk, J., ... Bommer, J.
1037 J. (2019). Simulations for the development of a ground motion model for induced
1038 seismicity in the Groningen gas field, The Netherlands. *Bulletin of Earthquake*
1039 *Engineering*, 17, 4441-4456.

1040

1041 Electric Power Research Institute (1993). Guidelines for determining design basis ground
1042 motions. Electric Power Research Institute EPRI TR- 102293, Palo Alto, California.

1043

1044 Evangelidis, C. P., Triantafyllis, N., Samios, M., Boukouras, K., Kontakos, K., Ktenidou, O.
1045 J., ... Tselentis, G. A. (2021). Seismic waveform data from Greece and Cyprus: Integration,
1046 archival, and open access. *Seismological Society of America*, 92(3), 1672-1684.

1047
1048 Fountoulakis, I., Evangelidis, C. P., Ktenidou, O. J. (2023). Coseismic and Postseismic
1049 Imaging of a Composite Fault System: The Samos 2020 M_w 7.0 Sequence. *Bulletin of the*
1050 *Seismological Society of America*, 113(3), 997-1012.
1051
1052 Greenland, S. (1980). The effect of misclassification in the presence of covariates.
1053 *American journal of epidemiology*, 112(4), 564-569.
1054
1055 Grendas, I., Theodoulidis, N., Hollender, F., Hatzidimitriou, P. (2021). A GIT algorithm for
1056 simultaneous estimation of seismic source, site response and regional-distance
1057 dependent attenuation parameters: application to synthetic and real data. *Journal of*
1058 *Seismology*, 25, 575-598.
1059
1060 Grendas, I., Theodoulidis, N., Hollender, F., Hatzidimitriou, P. (2022). Spectral
1061 decomposition of S-waves in investigating regional dependent attenuation and improving
1062 site amplification factors: A case study in western Greece. *Bulletin of Earthquake*
1063 *Engineering*, 20(12), 6441-6465.
1064
1065 Hartzell, S., Frankel, A., Liu, P., Zeng, Y., Rahman, S. (2011). Model and parametric
1066 uncertainty in source-based kinematic models of earthquake ground motion. *Bulletin of*
1067 *the Seismological Society of America*, 101(5), 2431-2452.
1068
1069 Higgins, M. D., Higgins, R. A. (1996). A geological companion to Greece and the Aegean,
1070 Cornell University Press, Ithaca, NY.
1071
1072 Huang, Y., Ellsworth, W. L., Beroza, G. C. (2017). Stress drops of induced and tectonic
1073 earthquakes in the central United States are indistinguishable. *Science advances*, 3(8),
1074 e1700772.
1075
1076 Huang, Y., Beroza, G. C., Ellsworth, W. L. (2016). Stress drop estimates of potentially
1077 induced earthquakes in the Guy-Greenbrier sequence. *Journal of Geophysical Research:*
1078 *Solid Earth*, 121(9), 6597-6607.
1079
1080 Joyner, W. B., Boore, D. M. (1981). Peak horizontal acceleration and velocity from strong-
1081 motion records including records from the 1979 Imperial Valley, California, earthquake.
1082 *Bulletin of the Seismological Society of America*, 71(6), 2011-2038.
1083
1084 Joyner, W. B., Boore, D. M. (1993). Methods for regression analysis of strong-motion data.
1085 *Bulletin of the Seismological Society of America*, 83(2), 469-487.
1086
1087 Karabulut, H., Z. Roumelioti, C. Benetatos, A. K. Mutlu, S. Özalaybey, M. Aktar, and A.
1088 Kiratzi (2006), A source study of the 6 July 2003 (M_w 5.7) earthquake sequence in the Gulf
1089 of Saros (Northern Aegean Sea): Seismological evidence for the western continuation of
1090 the Ganos fault, *Tectonophysics*, **412**, 195–216.

1091

1092 Karagianni, E., Papazachos, C. B., Panagiotopoulos, D., Suhadolc, P., Vuan, A., Panza, G.
 1093 (2005). Shear velocity structure in the Aegean area obtained by inversion of Rayleigh
 1094 waves. *Geophysical Journal International*, 160, 127–143.

1095

1096 Konstantinou, K. I., Melis, N. S. (2018). The relationship between local and moment
 1097 magnitude in Greece during the period 2008–2016. *Pure and Applied Geophysics*, 175,
 1098 731-740.

1099

1100 Koukouvelas, I. K., Aydin, A. (2002). Fault structure and related basins of the North Aegean
 1101 Sea and its surroundings. *Tectonics*, 21(5), 10-1.

1102

1103 Koukouzas, N., Lymperopoulos, P., Tasianas, A., Shariatipour, S. (2016). Feasibility study
 1104 for the setting up of a safety system for monitoring CO₂ storage at Prinos Field, Greece.
 1105 In: *IOP Conference Series: Earth and Environmental Science*, 44 (5), 052043, IOP
 1106 Publishing.

1107

1108 Koukouzas, N., Ziogou, F., Gemeni, V. (2009). Preliminary assessment of CO₂ geological
 1109 storage opportunities in Greece. *International Journal of Greenhouse Gas Control*, 3(4),
 1110 502-513.

1111

1112 Lam, N. (2023). A review of stochastic earthquake ground motion prediction equations
 1113 for stable regions. *International Journal of Advances in Engineering Sciences and Applied
 1114 Mathematics*, 15(1), 1-14.

1115

1116 Lavrentiadis, G., Abrahamson, N. A., Nicolas, K. M., Bozorgnia, Y., Goulet, C. A., Babič, A.,
 1117 ... Walling, M. (2023). Overview and introduction to development of non-ergodic
 1118 earthquake ground-motion models. *Bulletin of Earthquake Engineering*, 21(11), 5121-
 1119 5150.

1120

1121 Liou, I., & Abrahamson, N. (2025). Framework for aleatory variability and epistemic
 1122 uncertainty for the ground-motion characterization based on the level of simplification.
 1123 *Bulletin of the Seismological Society of America*, 115(1), 296-314.

1124

1125 Liu, X., Cotton, F., Fu, L., Chen, S., Li, X. (2025). Advancing ground-motion modeling
 1126 through data fusion? Insights combining NGA-West2 data and CyberShake simulations.
 1127 *Bulletin of Earthquake Engineering*, 1-22.

1128

1129 Lomax, A., Savvaidis, A. (2022) High-Precision Earthquake Location Using Source-Specific
 1130 Station Terms and Inter-Event Waveform Similarity. *Journal of Geophysical Research:
 1131 Solid Earth*, 127, e2021JB023190. <https://doi.org/10.1029/2021JB023190>

1132

1133 Makris, J., Papoulia, J., Yegorova, T. (2013). A 3-D density model of Greece constrained by
 1134 gravity and seismic data. *Geophysical Journal International*, 194(1), 1-17.

1135
1136 Margaris, B. N., Boore, D. M. (1998). Determination of $\Delta\sigma$ and K_0 from response spectra
1137 of large earthquakes in Greece. *Bulletin of the Seismological Society of America*, 88(1),
1138 170-182.
1139
1140 Margaris, B. N., Hatzidimitriou, P. M. (2002). Source spectral scaling and stress release
1141 estimates using strong-motion records in Greece. *Bulletin of the Seismological Society of*
1142 *America*, 92(3), 1040-1059.
1143
1144 McGarr, A., Simpson, D., Seeber, L. (2002). Case histories of induced and triggered
1145 seismicity. In *International Geophysics* (Vol. 81, pp. 647-661). Academic Press.
1146
1147 Omkar, Sharma, S., Bora, S. S., Mannu, U. (2026). Comparison of Stochastic Ground-
1148 Motion Simulation: SMSIM, EXSIM, and GMSS2.0. *Seismological Research Letters*,
1149 *accepted manuscript*.
1150
1151 Proedrou, P., Papaconstantinou, M. C. (2004). Prinos basin-a model for oil exploration.
1152 *Bulletin of the Geological Society of Greece*, 36(1), 327-333.
1153
1154 Proedrou, P., Sidiropoulos, T. (1992). Prinos Field-Greece Aegean Basin. Struct. Traps VI
1155 AAPG Spec. Vol. 1992, 275–291.
1156
1157 Rezaeian, S., Der Kiureghian, A. (2008). A stochastic ground motion model with separable
1158 temporal and spectral nonstationarities. *Earthquake Engineering and Structural*
1159 *Dynamics*, 37(13), 1565-1584.
1160
1161 Rezaeian, S., Hartzell, S., Sun, X., Mendoza, C. (2017). Simulation of earthquake ground
1162 motions in the eastern United States using deterministic physics-based and site-based
1163 stochastic approaches. *Bulletin of the Seismological Society of America*, 107(1), 149-168.
1164
1165 Rietbrock, A., Strasser, F., Edwards, B. (2013). A stochastic earthquake ground-motion
1166 prediction model for the United Kingdom. *Bulletin of the Seismological Society of America*,
1167 103(1), 57-77.
1168
1169 Rutqvist, J., Rinaldi, A. P., Cappa, F., Jeanne, P., Mazzoldi, A., Urpi, L., ... Vilarrasa, V. (2016).
1170 Fault activation and induced seismicity in geological carbon storage—Lessons learned from
1171 recent modeling studies. *Journal of Rock Mechanics and Geotechnical Engineering*, 8(6),
1172 789-804.
1173
1174 Schneider, J. F., Silva, W. J., Stark, C. (1993). Ground motion model for the 1989 M 6.9
1175 Loma Prieta earthquake including effects of source, path, and site. *Earthquake Spectra*,
1176 9(2), 251-287.
1177

1178 Shahjouei, A., Pezeshk, S. (2016). Alternative hybrid empirical ground-motion model for
1179 central and eastern North America using hybrid simulations and NGA-West2 models.
1180 *Bulletin of the Seismological Society of America*, 106(2), 734-754.
1181
1182 Sharbati, R., Khoshnoudian, F., Ramazi, H. R., Amindavar, H. R. (2018). Stochastic modeling
1183 and simulation of ground motions using complex discrete wavelet transform and
1184 Gaussian mixture model. *Soil Dynamics and Earthquake Engineering*, 114, 267-280.
1185
1186 Sotiriadis, D., Margaris, B., Klimis, N., Dokas, I. M. (2023). Seismic hazard in Greece: a
1187 comparative study for the region of East Macedonia and Thrace. *GeoHazards*, 4(3), 239-
1188 266.
1189
1190 Styron, R., Pagani, M. (2020). The GEM global active faults database. *Earthquake Spectra*,
1191 36, 160-180.
1192
1193 Sun, X., Hartzell, S., Rezaeian, S. (2015). Ground-motion simulation for the 23 August
1194 2011, Mineral, Virginia, earthquake using physics-based and stochastic broadband
1195 methods. *Bulletin of the Seismological Society of America*, 105(5), 2641-2661.
1196
1197 Sunny, J., De Angelis, M., Edwards, B. (2022). Ranking and Selection of Earthquake
1198 Ground-Motion Models Using the Stochastic Area Metric. *Seismological Society of
1199 America*, 93(2A), 787-797.
1200
1201 Suroyo, P. M., Sunny, J., Edwards, B. (2024). Physically adjusted ground motion prediction
1202 equations for induced seismicity at Preston New Road, UK. *Journal of Seismology*, 28(5),
1203 1147-1171.
1204
1205 Tani, F. C., Derras, B., Theodoulidis, N., Bard, P. Y. (2025). Towards site-specific ground
1206 motion estimates in Greece using a partially non-ergodic, mixed-effects, neural network
1207 approach. *Soil Dynamics and Earthquake Engineering*, 194, 109343.
1208
1209 Toro, G. R., Abrahamson, N. A., Schneider, J. F. (1997). Model of strong ground motions
1210 from earthquakes in central and eastern North America: best estimates and uncertainties.
1211 *Seismological research letters*, 68(1), 41-57.
1212
1213 Waldhauser, F., Ellsworth, W. L. (2000). A double-difference earthquake location
1214 algorithm: Method and application to the northern Hayward fault, California. *Bulletin of
1215 the seismological society of America*, 90(6), 1353-1368.
1216
1217 Walling, M., Kuehn, N. M., Abrahamson, N. A. (2021). An induced seismicity non-ergodic
1218 ground motion prediction equation (GMPE) in the Oklahoma region. *US Geol. Surv. Tech.
1219 Rept. NEHRP Grant G18AP00076*.
1220

1221 Wells, D. L., Coppersmith, K. J. (1994). New empirical relationships among magnitude,
1222 rupture length, rupture width, rupture area, and surface displacement. *Bulletin of the*
1223 *Seismological Society of America*, 84(4), 974-1002.
1224
1225 Yamamoto, Y., Baker, J. W. (2013). Stochastic model for earthquake ground motion using
1226 wavelet packets. *Bulletin of the Seismological Society of America*, 103(6), 3044-3056.
1227
1228 Yenier, E., Atkinson, G. M. (2015). An equivalent point-source model for stochastic
1229 simulation of earthquake ground motions in California. *Bulletin of the Seismological*
1230 *Society of America*, 105(3), 1435-1455.
1231
1232 Yenier, E., Atkinson, G. M., Sumy, D. F. (2017). Ground motions for induced earthquakes
1233 in Oklahoma. *Bulletin of the Seismological Society of America*, 107(1), 198-215.
1234
1235 Zaccarelli, R., Bindi, D., Strollo, A., Quinteros, J., Cotton, F. (2019). Stream2segment: An
1236 open-source tool for downloading, processing, and visualizing massive event-based
1237 seismic waveform datasets. *Seismological Research Letters*, 90(5), 2028-2038.
1238
1239 Zhu W. McBrearty I. W. Mousavi S. M. Ellsworth W. L., and Beroza G. C. 2022. Earthquake
1240 phase association using a Bayesian Gaussian Mixture Model, *J. Geophys. Res.* 127,
1241 e2021JB023249, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1029/2021JB023249>
1242
1243 Zhu W., and Beroza G. C. 2019. PhaseNet: A deep-neural-network-based seismic arrival-
1244 time picking method, *Geophys. J. Int.* 216, no. 1, 261–273.
1245
1246
1247
1248
1249
1250
1251
1252
1253
1254
1255
1256
1257
1258
1259
1260
1261
1262
1263
1264

1265 **AUTHORS' AFFILIATIONS**

1266

1267 **Marco Pilz**

1268 Helmholtz Center for Geosciences GFZ, Telegrafenberg, 14473 Potsdam, Germany

1269 pilz@gfz.de

1270

1271

1272 **Anastasia Kiratzi, Nikos Vavlas, Nikos Anterriotis-Kalpakidis**

1273 Aristotle University of Thessaloniki, Faculty of Sciences, Department of Geophysics, 54124

1274 Thessaloniki, Greece

1275 kiratzi@geo.auth.gr

1276 navavlas@geo.auth.gr

1277 nanterr@geo.auth.gr

1278 LIST OF FIGURE CAPTIONS

1279

1280 **Figure 1:** Geographical setting of the Prinos Complex (gray area polyline) and CO₂ storage
1281 site (inner polyline) within the northern Aegean Sea, fault structures (bold lines) taken
1282 from the fault database of the Global Earthquake Model (Styron and Pagani, 2020) and
1283 instrumental (after 1911) seismicity (white circles scaled with magnitude size). All
1284 earthquakes have moderate magnitudes ($M \leq 5$). Beach balls denote the few available
1285 focal mechanisms for the area of interest (light color: normal faulting; dark color: strike-
1286 slip faulting). The color version of this figure is available only in the electronic edition.

1287 Alt text: Topographical map around the Prinos Complex within a radius of around 50 km
1288 showing the spatial distribution of seismicity.

1289

1290 **Figure 2:** Epicentral distribution of the shallow ($h \leq 7$ km) events used in the study that
1291 occurred within a radius of 50 km around the Prinos storage complex (grey-shaded
1292 polyline in the central northern part of the map). Circles with dark color denote the 54
1293 manually reviewed shallow earthquakes, with magnitudes ranging from 0.6 to 3.5,
1294 forming the calibration dataset, alongside the corresponding station locations (squares).
1295 Light circles denote the 276 shallow, machine learning-derived events, with magnitudes
1296 ranging from 1.0 to 3.0, satisfying the relocation and quality criteria described in the text.
1297 Faults lines are as in Figure 1. The color version of this figure is available only in the
1298 electronic edition.

1299 Alt text: Topographical map of northern Greece and neighboring countries showing the
1300 spatial distribution of recorded events used for calibration and regression and the spatial
1301 distribution of seismic stations.

1302

1303 **Figure 3:** Comparison of SMSIM modelled peak ground acceleration (PGA) spectra for
1304 earthquake magnitudes M2 (black), M4 (red) and M6 (green) at two representative
1305 distances of (a) 5 km and (b) 30 km. Thick lines show the best-estimate parameter set
1306 while dashed lines show the results for the remaining four acceptable parameter subsets
1307 listed in Table 2. The color version of this figure is available only in the electronic edition.

1308 Alt text: Lines graph showing the modelled peak ground acceleration spectra for three
1309 different earthquake magnitudes against two hypocentral distances indicating a good
1310 agreement over the entire magnitude and distance range.

1311

1312 **Figure 4:** Modelled spectral intensities (top: PGA for moment magnitudes M2.5 (a) and
1313 M3.0 (b), PSA at $T = 0.2$ s (c) and PSA at $T = 0.5$ s (d) for moment magnitude M2.5) against
1314 hypocentral distance and comparison with various GMMs: Atkinson (2015, solid line),
1315 Bommer et al. (2022, dashed line), Douglas et al. (2013, dotted line), Suroyo et al. (2024,
1316 loosely dashed line) and Yenier et al. (2017, dashed-dotted line). Synthetic (black circles)
1317 and recorded (black triangles) data with magnitude values ± 0.2 given in each plot are
1318 overlain.

1319 Alt text: Line graphs showing the modelled and recorded spectral intensities for two
1320 different magnitudes and for different spectral periods against hypocentral distance
1321 indicating varying levels of agreement with various existing GMMs for induced seismicity.

1322

1323 **Figure 5:** Residuals (\log_{10} scale), i.e., recorded (crosses, both the original 54 events and
1324 the additional 276 machine learning-derived) and modelled (circles) minus predicted PGA
1325 (a,b) and PSA at $T = 0.5$ s (c,d) using the newly derived hybrid GMM shown versus moment
1326 magnitude (a,c) and hypocentral distance (b,d). Modelling was carried out on 0.1-
1327 magnitude and 2.5 km distance grid. Mean and standard deviations for various magnitude
1328 and distance bins are also shown (herein, each magnitude bin corresponds to one unit of
1329 magnitude, and each distance bin corresponds to 20 km).

1330 Alt text: Residuals of the newly derived hybrid GMM for two different spectral periods
1331 indicating no significant under- or overprediction of the entire magnitude and distance
1332 ranges.

1333

1334 **Figure 6:** Predicted PGA values for reference rock conditions ($v_{S30} = 760$ m/s) based on
1335 different GMMs listed in Table 3 within their applicability ranges: [Atkinson \(2015\)](#), solid
1336 lines), [Bommer et al. \(2022\)](#), dashed lines), [Douglas et al. \(2013\)](#), dotted lines), [Yenier et al.](#)
1337 [\(2017\)](#), dashed-dotted lines) and [Suroyo et al. \(2024\)](#), loosely dashed lines) and our new
1338 hybrid GMM model (thick solid lines) for moment magnitudes M2 (black), M3 (green), M4
1339 (red) and M5 (blue). The color version of this figure is available only in the electronic
1340 edition.

1341 Alt text: Line plot showing the level of PGA based on the newly derived hybrid GMM and
1342 other existing GMMs for induced seismicity for four different magnitudes indicating the
1343 new GMM takes a middle position between the other models but shows a more moderate
1344 decay with distance.

1345

1346 **Figure 7:** Spatial distribution of PGA around the Prinos CO₂ storage site as predicted by
1347 the hybrid GMM developed in this study (*left column*) and by the combination of the
1348 GMMs listed in Table 3 (*right column*, equal weights) for reference rock conditions
1349 ($v_{S30} = 760$ m/s). Each row corresponds to a different earthquake moment magnitude
1350 scenario (M3.0, 4.0 and 4.5). The red star marks the assumed epicenter. Solid isolines
1351 correspond to PGA intervals. The color version of this figure is available only in the
1352 electronic edition.

1353 Alt text: ShakeMaps comparing the spatial distribution of ground motion of the new
1354 hybrid GMM and other GMMs indicating a symmetrical decay from the epicentral region
1355 with the hybrid GMM showing slightly lower PGA amplitudes in the near-field for the
1356 larger magnitude scenarios and a more moderate decay.

1357

1358

1359

1360

1361

1362 **LIST OF TABLES**

1363

1364 **Table 1**

1365 Starting model parameter space used in the stochastic synthetic simulations in the Prinos-

1366 Kavala basin.

1367

Parameter	Adopted Value	Reference
Source spectrum model	Single-corner source model	Brune (1970, 1971)
Stress parameter $\Delta\sigma$ [bar]	$1 < \Delta\sigma < 100$ logarithmically spaced	Margaris and Boore (1998); Margaris and Hatzidimitriou (2002); Grendas et al. (2021, 2022)
Shear-wave velocity at source depth [km/s]	3.42	Karagianni et al. (2005)
Density at source depth [kg/m ³]	2810	Makris et al. (2013)
Radiation pattern	0.55	Boore and Boatwright (1984)
Geometrical spreading	$r^{-1.47}$ for $r < 12$ km $r^{-1.06}$ for $12 \text{ km} < r < 53$ km $r^{-0.35}$ for $r > 53$ km	Bindi et al. (2023)
Reference quality factor Q_0	$50 < Q_0 < 300$ with steps of 25	Bommer et al. (2017); Grendas et al. (2021); Bindi et al. (2023)
Frequency exponent η	$0.60 < \eta < 0.85$ with step of 0.05	
Kappa K_0 [s]	$0.035 < K_0 < 0.055$ with steps of 0.005	Margaris and Boore (1998)

1368

1369

1370 **Table 2**

1371 Five retained parameter subsets satisfying the 95% confidence bounds across all spectral
 1372 periods. The subset with AM = 0.81 represents the minimum-misfit and is adopted as
 1373 the best-estimate model.

Parameter	AM = 0.81	AM = 0.84	AM = 0.85	AM = 0.86	AM = 0.86
Stress parameter $\Delta\sigma$ [bar]	26	13	41	16	40
Reference quality factor Q_0	236	222	225	231	247
Frequency exponent η	0.69	0.66	0.65	0.69	0.73
Kappa K_0 [s]	0.048	0.046	0.046	0.047	0.051

1374

1375

1376 **Table 3**

1377 Representative ground motion models (GMMs) developed for induced seismicity,
 1378 including applicable magnitude and distance ranges, focal-depth coverage and site-class
 1379 assumptions.

1380

Reference	Region	Magnitude range	Distance range [km]	Depth range [km]	Model type	Site class
Atkinson (2015)	North America (NGA-West2)	3 – 6	< 40	< 10	Empirical (regression)	Rock/stiff soil
Bommer et al. (2022)	Groningen, Netherlands	< 4	< 60	< 2–3	Empirical	Stiff clay/sand over rock
Douglas et al. (2013)	Basel (CH), Campi Flegrei (IT), Geysers (US), Hengill (IS), Roswinkel and Voerendaal (NL), Soultz-sous-Forêts (FR)	1–5	< 20	shallow	Simulation (stochastic + empirical)	Site-specific
Suroyo et al. (2024)	Preston New Road, UK	< 4	< 30	≤ 5	Physically-adjusted empirical	Hard/stiff soil
Yenier et al. (2017)	Oklahoma, USA	3–6	3–150	shallow	Simulation-based (stochastic)	Rock (regional average)

1381

1382

1383 **Table 4**

1384 Calibrated coefficients of the hybrid GMM derived in this study. Periods $T = 0.01$ to 1.0 s
 1385 refer to 5%-damped spectral acceleration in \log_{10} units. The value at $T = 0.01$ s is used as
 1386 a proxy for PGA with ground-motion amplitudes expressed in m/s^2 . Variability terms
 1387 include total standard deviation σ , between-event variability τ and within-event
 1388 variability φ .

Period T [s]	c_0	c_1	c_2	c_{3a}	c_{3b}	σ	τ	φ
0.01	-2.25	1.14	-0.04	-2.21	-1.76	0.58	0.38	0.43
0.03	-2.04	1.05	-0.02	-2.19	-1.76	0.54	0.35	0.41
0.05	-1.45	0.89	-0.01	-2.17	-1.73	0.51	0.33	0.39
0.1	-1.89	1.11	-0.04	-2.13	-1.71	0.48	0.29	0.38
0.2	-3.12	1.52	-0.08	-2.08	-1.65	0.45	0.30	0.34
0.3	-3.87	1.73	-0.09	-2.08	-1.61	0.43	0.29	0.32
0.5	-4.88	1.91	-0.10	-2.07	-1.58	0.46	0.31	0.34
1.0	-5.46	2.17	-0.08	-2.05	-1.49	0.49	0.32	0.37

1389

1390

1391

1392

1393

1394

1395

1396

1397

1398

1399 **Supporting information for**

1400

1401 **Hybrid ground-motion model for potential induced seismicity at**
1402 **the Prinos CO₂ storage site (northern Greece)**

1403

1404

1405 Marco Pilz¹, Anastasia Kiratzi², Nikos Vavlas², Nikos Anterriotis-Kalpakidis²

1406

1407 1 Helmholtz Center for Geosciences GFZ, Telegrafenberg, 14473 Potsdam, Germany

1408 2 Aristotle University of Thessaloniki, Faculty of Sciences, Department of Geophysics,

1409 54124 Thessaloniki, Greece

1410

1411

1412 Corresponding author: Marco Pilz, pilz@gfz.de

1413

1414 The supplementary material contains the following:

1415

1416 A) *Figures S1 to S3*

1417 Calibration of the simulation model parameters based on the dataset of 54 manually analysed
1418 shallow events, including information on magnitude, depth and distance from the Prinos
1419 storage site.

1420 **Figure S1.** Distribution of distance from the Prinos storage site versus ML magnitude.

1421 **Figure S2.** Distribution of ML magnitude as a function of focal depth.

1422 **Figure S3.** Number of observations per depth bin for the 54-event calibration dataset.

1423

1424 B) Figures S4 to S7

1425 Information on magnitude, depth and distance from the Prinos storage site for the 276
1426 machine-learning–derived events used for the regression stage of the hybrid ground-motion
1427 model, together with the quadratic regression used to convert machine-learning ML values to
1428 ML magnitudes consistent with the NOA manual catalogue.

1429 **Figure S4.** Distribution of distance from the storage site versus NOA-calibrated ML magnitude.

1430 **Figure S5.** Distribution of NOA-calibrated ML magnitude as a function of focal depth.

1431 **Figure S6.** Number of observations per depth bin for the machine-learning catalogue.

1432 **Figure S7.** Quadratic calibration model used to convert GaMMA-derived ML values to
1433 magnitudes consistent with the NOA manually reviewed catalogue (NOA-ML).

1434

1435 C) Figures S8 to S10

1436 Scenario comparisons of the spatial distribution of PGA around the Prinos CO₂ storage site for
1437 three assumed earthquake scenarios, using the hybrid GMM developed in this study and the
1438 prediction equations of Abrahamson (2015), Bommer et al. (2022), Douglas et al. (2013), Suroyo
1439 et al. (2024) and Yenier et al. (2017) for reference rock conditions ($V_{S30} = 760$ m/s).

1440 **Figure S8.** Scenario ShakeMap comparisons for an $M = 3.0$ earthquake at 3 km depth.

1441 **Figure S9.** Same as Figure S8 but for an $M = 4.0$ earthquake.

1442 **Figure S10.** Same as Figure S8 but for an $M = 4.5$ earthquake.

1443

1444 D) Tables S1 to S2

1445 Mixed effect regression results for the coefficients of the GMM and corresponding residuals
1446 based on various data sets.

1447 **Table S1.** Calibrated regression coefficients of the hybrid GMM derived in this study using the
1448 full dataset with assigning a weight of 0.5 to the simulation data.

1449 **Table S2.** Calibrated regression coefficients of the hybrid GMM derived in this study excluding
1450 machine learning-derived events.

1451

1452 *References*

1453 Atkinson, G. M. (2015). Ground-motion prediction equation for small-to-moderate events at
1454 short hypocentral distances, with application to induced-seismicity hazards. *Bulletin of the*
1455 *Seismological Society of America*, 105(2A), 981–992.

1456 Bommer, J. J., Stafford, P. J., Ruigrok, E., Rodriguez-Marek, A., Ntinalexis, M., Kruiver, P. P., ...
1457 van Elk, J. (2022). Ground-motion prediction models for induced earthquakes in the Groningen
1458 gas field, the Netherlands. *Journal of Seismology*, 26(6), 1157–1184.

1459 Douglas, J., Edwards, B., Convertito, V., Sharma, N., Tramelli, A., Kraaijpoel, D., ... Troise, C.
1460 (2013). Predicting ground motion from induced earthquakes in geothermal areas. *Bulletin of*
1461 *the Seismological Society of America*, 103(3), 1875–1897.

1462 Suroyo, P. M., Sunny, J., & Edwards, B. (2024). Physically adjusted ground-motion prediction
1463 equations for induced seismicity at Preston New Road, UK. *Journal of Seismology*, 28(5), 1147–
1464 1171.

1465 Yenier, E., Atkinson, G. M., & Sumy, D. F. (2017). Ground motions for induced earthquakes in
1466 Oklahoma. *Bulletin of the Seismological Society of America*, 107(1), 198–215.

1467

1468

1469

1470

1471

1472

1473 **Figure S1:** Distribution of distance from the Prinos storage site versus ML magnitude.

1474

1475

1476 **Figure S2:** Distribution of ML magnitude as a function of focal depth.

1477

1478

1479 **Figure S3:** Number of observations per depth bin for the 54-event calibration dataset.

1480

1481

1482

1483 **Figure S4:** Distribution of distance from the storage site for the machine learning-derived
 1484 events versus NOA-calibrated ML magnitude.

1485

1486 **Figure S5:** Distribution of NOA-calibrated ML magnitude as a function of focal depth.

1487

1488

1489 **Figure S6:** Number of observations per depth bin for the machine-learning catalogue.

1490

1491 **Figure S7:** Quadratic calibration model used to convert GaMMA-derived ML values to
 1492 magnitudes consistent with the NOA manually reviewed catalogue (NOA-ML).

1493

1494 **Figure S8:** Scenario ShakeMap comparisons of the spatial distribution of PGA for an M_{3.0}
 1495 earthquake at 3 km depth based on the hybrid GMM developed in this study and the equations
 1496 of Abrahamson (2015), Bommer et al. (2022), Douglas et al. (2013), Suroyo et al. (2024) and
 1497 Yenier et al. (2017) for reference rock conditions ($v_{S30} = 760$ m/s).

1498

1499 Figure S9: Same as Figure S8 but for an M4.0 earthquake.

1500

1501 **Figure S10:** Same as Figure S8 but for an M4.5 earthquake.

1502

1503 **Table S1:** Calibrated regression coefficients of the hybrid GMM derived in this study using
 1504 the full dataset with assigning a weight of 0.5 to the simulation data.

Period T [s]	c_0	c_1	c_2	c_{3a}	c_{3b}	σ	τ	φ
0.01	-2.25	1.14	-0.04	-2.21	-1.76	0.51	0.38	0.40
0.03	-2.04	1.05	-0.02	-2.19	-1.76	0.55	0.35	0.42
0.05	-1.45	0.89	-0.01	-2.17	-1.73	0.53	0.34	0.55
0.1	-1.89	1.11	-0.04	-2.13	-1.71	0.49	0.29	0.44
0.2	-3.12	1.52	-0.08	-2.08	-1.65	0.46	0.28	0.43
0.3	-3.87	1.73	-0.09	-2.08	-1.61	0.44	0.29	0.38
0.5	-4.88	1.91	-0.10	-2.07	-1.58	0.45	0.30	0.35
1.0	-5.46	2.17	-0.08	-2.05	-1.49	0.45	0.32	0.31

1505

1506

1507 **Table S2:** Calibrated regression coefficients of the hybrid GMM derived in this study
 1508 excluding machine learning-derived events.

Period T [s]	c_0	c_1	c_2	c_{3a}	c_{3b}	σ	τ	φ
0.01	-2.53	1.37	-0.07	-2.28	-1.59	0.50	0.37	0.34
0.03	-2.16	1.24	-0.06	-2.29	-1.60	0.47	0.34	0.32
0.05	-1.62	1.08	-0.05	-2.28	-1.63	0.45	0.32	0.32
0.1	-2.16	1.40	-0.08	-2.24	-1.61	0.40	0.28	0.29
0.2	-3.29	1.81	-0.12	-2.19	-1.55	0.39	0.28	0.27
0.3	-4.04	2.03	-0.13	-2.17	-1.51	0.36	0.27	0.24
0.5	-4.92	2.21	-0.14	-2.15	-1.48	0.40	0.29	0.27
1.0	-5.62	2.16	-0.12	-2.12	-1.43	0.42	0.30	0.30

1509

1510